

OPTICAL COMPUTATIONAL GEOMETRY

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by
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Abstract

In spite of the enormous achievements in the development of electronic computers over the past 30 years, there has always been a steady interest in optical computers as a potential alternative computing technology, ever since invention of the laser and of optical correlators in the early sixties. A major motivation is that the practical speed of an electronic signal on a silicon chip is roughly only one-fifth of the speed of light and in wires it slows down even further [J], whereas an optical signal always travels at the speed of light.

This potential advantage of optical computers over electronic computers has been the main driving force in efforts to create such an optical computer. However, in addition to this hardware issue, there is also the issue of software efficiency – namely the time-complexity of algorithms designed for such hardware. The potential advantages of optical computers from the viewpoint of software efficiency has not yet been thoroughly investigated to date.

A major goal of this thesis is to bridge this gap and demonstrate that optical computers do indeed facilitate reduction in the time-complexity of algorithms, to an extent unachievable by multiprocessor electronic computers.

As an application area, we have focussed mostly on problems in computational geometry, both because it is an important area in computer science, and because in most (2-dimensional) problems in computational geometry both input and output data are easy to represent in optical computers. Using a plausible model of optical computation, we have shown that most of the basic problems of planar computational geometry can be solved in a constant number of elementary optical operations. Thus, at least theoretically so far, optics appear to outperform electronics.

The present thesis summarises our investigations on the subject of the design and analysis of optical algorithms in computational geometry and other areas. The thesis is organized as follows:

- The introduction contains the background material for the subsequent chapters. We introduce various optical computational models: continuous and discrete, in terms of set theory and in terms of logic. In comparison with computational models for electronic computers, our models contain new elementary data types, 2-dimensional matrices and bivariate functions, on which various (and often complicated) mathematical operations can be performed optically in constant time. We give a comprehensive list of these operations, each of which has been demonstrated in the literature to be implementable on standard optical devices. However, at present there does not exist a full-fledged optical computer capable of performing all of these operations. Nevertheless, based on the tremendous recent progress in optical computing, it seems likely that the implementation of such computer will take place in the not-too-distant future. We also mention and classify special and general purpose optical computers that have been constructed during the past few years (none of which, though, fully conforms yet to our model).
- Chapter 2 presents the formalization of the analogy between the Minkowski sum and convolution [GRS], which gives rise to a constant time optical algorithm for computing the Minkowski sum of two planar figures. Furthermore, we show that some basic problems,

such as reconstruction of the interior of a figure, hidden line removal, and visibility from a point at infinity, have fairly simple solutions that are based on computing Minkowski sums, and thus can also be solved optically in constant time. We also show that some problems which, at first sight, have nothing to do with computing Minkowski sums, such as drawing a sector between a curve and a point, can be reduced to a Minkowski sum computation after a log-polar change of coordinates. Based on this technique we propose our first and simplest optical convex hull algorithm, which requires $O(N)$ optical steps (this will be improved substantially later on). We also show, that with proper change of coordinates, it is possible to represent many complex images as the Minkowski sum of a simple image with a point set, and apply this technique to derive an algorithm for radii-to-rings mapping, which will be needed later on.

- Chapter 3 contains the background for optical computation in parallel, using polychromatic light. Many images, each represented by a different color, can be “multiplexed” together into a single polychromatic image, and can thus be processed in parallel by the same optical hardware, provided the operations on them are identical. Thus, we show that a SIMD (Single Instruction Multiple Data) optical computer, unlike its electronic counterpart, can be implemented using a single processor. We also demonstrate the technique of converting serial optical algorithms having $O(N)$ time complexity into constant time optical SIMD algorithms, using this polychromatic method.

- Chapter 4 describes optical realization of geometric duality and its application to constructing a convex hull in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.

- In Chapter 5 we introduce the notions of brightness of the Minkowski sum and unions of figures, and show how it can be used to filter out certain portions of images. In particular, we show how to filter segments from an image that also contains isolated points. We also present solutions to various problems in computational geometry based on numerous computational tricks which involves the filtering property of the Minkowski sums and transitions from the original plane to a dual plane and back.

- In Chapter 6 we first use the discrete model of optical computation to tackle a problem which cannot be satisfactorily solved in the continuous model. This is the problem of reconstructing the interior of a figure from its boundary. We show that if the boundary is represented in discrete pixelwise form and the image to be reconstructed has no holes, then the reconstruction (also called filling) can be performed optically in constant time.

- We continue to deal with the discrete model of optical computation in Chapter 7, and present a constant-time optical sorting algorithm, based on efficient optical matrix operations.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In the last several years there has been significant progress in the design of optical devices that can perform miscellaneous computational tasks. The input to some of such devices is an *optical frame* (also known as *spatial light modulator*, or SLM in short), which is a 2-dimensional function, $f(x, y)$ (or several such functions), encoded in some optical form, such as a plane light wave with variable amplitude, or with variable phase, or as a planar slab made of optical material with variable transmittance coefficient, etc. The optical device then takes the input frames, and pass them through various lenses, mirrors, beamsplitters, fibers, holograms, possibly also interacting several input frames with each other. In this manner a variety of output frames can be generated, some of which are fairly complex functions of the input frames. In particular, in a constant number of operations, one can compute various pointwise arithmetic operations on the input frames (addition, subtraction, multiplication), compute Fourier transforms, convolutions, ‘semi-conformal’ transformations of the coordinate system (defined in more detail below), thresholding the image at a specified level of intensity, and many other operations. The output frames can then be stored in various ways, similar to those in which the input frames are represented, and then be used as inputs for further optical operations. The resolution of optical frames is getting progressively higher, and nowadays it is possible to store several million “pixels” on a single frame.

The power of optical computing can be further magnified by ‘multiplexing’ many ‘monochromatic’ optical frames, each with a different light frequency, into a single ‘polychromatic’ frame, performing some optical operation on that frame, and then ‘demultiplexing’ the output into its monochromatic constituents. This operation achieves the effect of performing the same optical operation simultaneously on all input frames. Thus, optical computing offers a high degree of parallelism, on top of the parallelism already available from pointwise (and other) operations on 2-d frames. (Nevertheless, in what follows we will strongly prefer optical algorithms that operate in the monochromatic mode, because the transformation from many monochromatic frames into a single polychromatic frame and back is more complex to perform.) Finally, there are various techniques to transfer data between a conventional electronic computer and optical frames (although this transfer is usually a

bottleneck in optical computing).

These technological advances open up the possibility of constructing full-fledged general-purpose optical computers, both analog and digital, with a processing unit capable of executing any program consisting of optical and other auxiliary operations. At present such computers are not yet available, although various projects are currently studying the construction of prototypes of such computers and success in some of them have been reported. For example, an all-optical digital processor with feedback has been created at AT&T [PGDLDCM]. Even though this processor cannot store a program to be executed, this drawback has been recently overcome in an optical computer created at the University of Colorado at Boulder [MFHJF].

From an algorithmic point of view, optical computing opens up immensely powerful new opportunities for speeding up the solutions of many basic problems. This is because various complex operations, that normally are fairly expensive, can now be performed in constant time. Despite this, very few optical algorithms of interest to the computer science community have been proposed to date, and they mainly involve sorting [SA, RT, SB, K91].

There are two reasons why computer science research has been slow in the study of optical algorithms:

The first is that, until recently, practically all designers of optical algorithms have come from the optical engineering community, and not from the computer science community. Therefore, they were mostly concerned with the design and constructions of optical devices, each designed to solve a single algorithmic task, and mostly neglected the issue of algorithmic design, in the classical computer science spirit.

The second reason is that the design and analysis of optical algorithms is a radically new field where most of the common computational tricks of standard computer science, like divide-and-conquer, prune-and-search, binary trees, etc., are not well suited. They can be applied, but obviously cannot give rise to constant time algorithms, which are the ultimate goal in optical computing, because over-constant time algorithms can often be achieved by using multiprocessor electronic computers.

To achieve $O(1)$ time complexity, one needs to develop an arsenal of new computational tricks, capable of realizing the massive parallelism offered by optical computing. Computational geometry is an ideal field for the development of such tricks, and of optical algorithms in general, because the basic optical ‘data type’, the optical frame, is an ideal medium for representing (two-dimensional) geometric data. In fact, in many geometric algorithms (in robotics, computer vision, image processing, object recognition, etc.) the data already exist in the form of 2-d images, so direct optical manipulations of such images, besides being ultra-fast, will also save the need to transform such images from raster to vector representation and back. In more ‘artificial’ cases, when the input to a problem is given in a discrete combinatorial fashion (e.g. a set of n points or n lines in the plane), there arises the technical issue of creating an optical frame containing this input. However, once the input frame has been created, we can apply to it the whole arsenal of optical operations and obtain very fast algorithms.

Computational geometry is an ideal field for developing optical algorithms also because

many of its problems require that their output be drawn graphically on the screen of an optical device. Such a drawing is an analog computation which can be readily performed optically.

Of course, if one examines the optical computational model proposed below in a skeptic and critical manner, one will find various objections to the constant-time claim. For example, when the data size is enormous, it will not fit into a single optical frame, and then the number of frames needed to store the data will affect the physical dimensions of the optical computer, and consequently also affect the time it takes light to travel from an input to an output frame. Other objections of a similar nature can also be raised. The situation is very similar to the status of parallel algorithms about 10 years ago, where similar objections were raised, and were overcome by simply ignoring them, and by introducing the abstract model of the PRAM, which turned out to be extremely successful in the study of parallel algorithms, even though it was clear that transforming algorithms designed for a PRAM to real parallel machines will always be problematic and require more work. We propose to follow a similar approach to optical computing. That is, to introduce an abstract model in which the basic optical operations are all fast (take constant time), and study various algorithms under this model, obtaining very fast performance for them. The model has been briefly mentioned above, and is described in detail below. Besides the theoretical interest in such an approach, we believe that it will be useful also pragmatically, because it will highlight desired design issues, whose implementation will make future optical computers a much more convenient tool. Engineers currently working on the design of optical computers may be unaware of these ‘software’ issues, and further theoretical research on optical algorithms, like that presented in this thesis, will most likely have a significant impact on their work.

In this chapter we provide background material on optical computing, including basic terminology and underlying physical principles of optical image processing, and optical models of computations.

1.1 An Optical Computational Model

1.1.1 New elementary data types provided by optical computers

Optical image processing techniques deal with 2-dimensional images of two kinds: plane light waves

$$\vec{A}(x, y) \cdot e^{i \cdot \psi(x, y, t)},$$

and distributions of the transmittance, reflectance or refraction coefficient of planar slabs of material. Images in the form of light wave are subdivided in turn into the following subtypes depending on which physical magnitude represents the two-dimensional distribution $f(x, y)$:

- **images based on amplitude modulation of light:**

$$\vec{A}(x, y) \cdot e^{i \cdot \psi(x, y, t)} = f(x, y) \cdot e^{i \cdot (\omega t + \text{const})};$$

- **images based on phase modulation of light:**

$$\vec{A}(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)} = \vec{A} \cdot e^{i(\omega t + f(x, y))}.$$

Both types of images (plane lightwaves and distributions of either coefficient of a planar material) can be converted into each other. It is obvious how to transform, for example, transparency distribution of a material into distribution of amplitude of a light — simply pass a plane light wave through the material. The inverse transformation is provided by photomaterials which change their transmission coefficient as a function of the amplitude of an incident light [ATE], [MA].

At present, two dimensional distributions of transmittance (or reflectance, or refraction) coefficient can be generated and updated in real time only on special devices called *spatial light modulators* (SLM) which represent images in discrete pixelwise form. Transmittance/reflectance coefficient of pixels in these devices can be controlled both optically and electronically, where the first method is preferable because it allows pixels to be controlled in parallel.

Optical control of the transmittance coefficient proceeds as follows. Let A_{ij} be the amplitude of an incident plane lightwave at pixel (i, j) . If the SLM is in control mode, then the transmittance coefficient of the pixel becomes A_{ij} (in working mode the SLM simply transmits the incident light through each pixel, relaxing its amplitude proportionally to the optical density of the pixel).

Thus, the first new elementary data type provided by optical computers are two dimensional matrices A_{mn} . The resolution of SLM's is getting progressively higher and nowadays it approaches 10000 pixels per mm, better than a high resolution photographic film [STCWDGPC]. Hence, it is reasonable to assume (with a high degree of approximation) that continuous bivariate functions can also be represented as a second new elementary data type provided by optical computers.

These two data types give rise to different and supplementary models of optical computations: discrete and continuous. Even though most geometric problems are easier to treat in the continuous model, there are also problems which are better tackled in the discrete one. Therefore, we will elaborate on both models.

1.1.2 Elementary continuous optical operations

Obviously, two waves $A_1(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$ and $A_2(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$ can be added to yield a new wave $(A_1(x, y) + A_2(x, y)) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$ whose amplitude $A_1(x, y) + A_2(x, y)$ can be “written” onto an SLM as a transparency distribution. Thus, we can perform addition of two bivariate functions in a single optical step.

We can also perform subtraction by lengthening the distance traversed by the first wave before it meets another wave [E]. The lengthening should turn the wave $A_1(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$ into $A_1(x, y) \cdot e^{i(\psi(x, y, t) + \pi)} = -A_1(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$ in the plane where it meets the wave $A_2(x, y) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$. Superposition of these two waves yields the new wave $(A_2(x, y) - A_1(x, y)) \cdot e^{i\psi(x, y, t)}$, and we again can “write” its amplitude onto an SLM.

However, this simplest approach to optical image addition and subtraction is very poor in practice, and optical scientists have developed significantly more reliable and complicated schemes [M], [FN]. Nevertheless, it provides enough intuition to understand that optically we can perform

- **pointwise addition/subtraction:** $h(x, y) = f(x, y) \pm g(x, y)$ in parallel for every (x, y) in a given range, so that these operations can be regarded as elementary optical operations, because they can be performed in constant time.

Similarly, the following operations have also been shown to be elementary (constant time) optical operations:

- **pointwise multiplication:** $h(x, y) = f(x, y) \times g(x, y)$, which is achieved by cascading a light wave through two transparencies $f(x, y)$ and $g(x, y)$ respectively [W], provided both $f(x, y)$ and $g(x, y)$ do not exceed 1. Otherwise, the multiplication can be performed with the help of so called “four wave mixing” in a photorefractive crystal [WY].

- **scalar multiplication:** $g(x, y) = M \times f(x, y)$. If $M < 1$ this is readily performed by passing the light wave through a transparent matter of optical density M . If $M > 1$ then optical signal amplification can be performed with the help of a specific physical effect in photorefractive crystals called “two-wave mixing” [HCY].

- **complementation:** $g(x, y) = I_{max} - f(x, y)$, where $I_{max} \geq f(x, y)$ for all x, y [WT, OHG].

- **thresholding at given level of intensity** [GCHHZY]:

$$g(x, y) = Threshold_a(f(x, y)) = \begin{cases} f(x, y), & \text{if } f(x, y) > a; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

- **sine-transformation** [C]:

$$g(x, y) = f(x, y) \cdot \sin(aV(x, y)),$$

where $V(x, y)$ is the voltage distribution across an SLM. Since incident light wave of amplitude $f(x, y)$ can be converted into voltage $f^2(x, y)$ [F], then we can assume that the transformation

$$g(x, y) = f(x, y) \cdot \sin(a \cdot f^2(x, y))$$

is also an elementary operation in our model.

- **semi-conformal change of coordinates:**

$$g(x, y) = f(u^{-1}(x, y), v^{-1}(x, y)),$$

for any geometric transformation $u = u(x, y)$, $v = v(x, y)$, which satisfies the condition ([SC], [B1], [B2], [GT], [GET]):

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x}.$$

Optical realization of any specific transformation of this kind requires a special computer generated hologram (CGH) which looks like a collection of many microscopic gratings. Each grating bends the incoming ray depending on its frequency and on the orientation of the

Figure 1.1: A CGH produces coordinate transformation of an input image

grating. Therefore, by passing an image through such a set of gratings, one can redirect light from each point in the input plane to a new point in the output plane (see Fig. 1.1).

A number of such holograms may be prepared beforehand and kept in the optical memory of the computer as a library of useful geometric transformations.

A geometric transformation may not satisfy the condition mentioned above. This is, for example, the case of the standard polar transformation

$$u = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2},$$

$$v = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y}{x}\right).$$

In such cases we can often express such a transformation as a sequence of other semi-conformal transformations. The above example can be performed as a combination of the *log-polar* transformation

$$u = \ln \sqrt{x^2 + y^2},$$

$$v = -\tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y}{x}\right);$$

and the transformation

$$u = e^x,$$

$$v = -y,$$

each of which does satisfy the required condition.

Remark: It is worth mentioning that any coordinate transformation (not only semi-conformal) can be performed in a single step via a matrix of holograms (called a multi-faceted holographic optical elements [G81, BCa]). However, the quality of a transformation by a single CGH is much better than that achieved by a matrix of holograms. Even the

cartesian-to-polar mapping is better performed in two steps by the above semi-conformal transformations than in a single step by a matrix of holograms [Fa].

There is also another objection to including transformations by matrix of holograms in our model of computation: To transform $N \times N$ pixels one needs a matrix of $N \times N$ holograms. This means that such transformations are not applicable to SLMs with resolution exceeding the dimension of the matrix. At present there exist SLMs with resolution well above 1000×1000 pixels, whereas the largest dimension of a matrix of holograms achieved so far is 256×256 [AFEL]. Obviously, the dimension of a matrix of holograms will most likely always lag well behind the highest resolution achieved by an SLM.

Therefore, in what follows we strongly prefer to use only semi-conformal changes of coordinates, effected by a single CGH.

• **1-dimensional Fourier transform:**

$F(x, v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y)e^{-ivy} dy$ for every (x, v) simultaneously; this is achieved by passing the light wave through a cylindrical lens [LS].

• **2-dimensional Fourier transform** (see [R], [G]):

$$F(u, v) = \int \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y)e^{-i(xu+yv)} dx dy,$$

which is achieved by passing the light wave through a spherical lens.

• **Hough transform:**

$$p = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta,$$

which maps any point (x, y) in the image plane onto the above sinusoidal curve in the Hough plane (p, θ) [DH]. In particular, a straight line

$$ax + by = 1$$

is mapped onto the image

$$\{(p, \theta) \mid \exists x, y \ (ax + by = 1 \ \& \ p = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta)\},$$

which has a peak of intensity at the point

$$p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}, \quad \theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{b}{a}\right),$$

because all the sinusoidal curves forming this image pass through this point.

This transform is used to recognize, locate and enhance straight lines in images. For this goal, the original image is mapped onto the Hough plane, where significant peaks of intensity are thresholded and then these peaks are transformed into straight lines, which become smooth and without discontinuities and noisy distortions.

Optical realization of the Hough transform [GGSBCG] is based on performing the Radon transform

$$R(p, \theta) = \int \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y)\delta(p - x \cos \theta - y \sin \theta) dx dy,$$

which can be shown to yield the same results as the Hough transform for binary images [D].

• **theta-modulation** ([AL], [BLS]), which provides the following transformation:

$$f(x, y) \longrightarrow \cos(x \cdot \cos(f(x, y)) + y \cdot \sin(f(x, y))),$$

where $f(x, y)$ denotes the brightness of an image at the point (x, y) .

It is easily seen that the Fourier transform of a theta-modulated function $f(x, y)$ results in the image $\{(u, v) | u = \pm \cos(f(x, y)), v = \pm \sin(f(x, y))\}$.

Thus, theta-modulation allows us to transform intensity of a point (x, y) into a pair of points on the unit circle whose angular deviation from the X-axis is proportional to the intensity.

Besides these elementary operations, optical computers can also perform the following more complicated but useful operations (each requiring a constant number of elementary operations):

• **convolution** [V]:

$$h(x, y) = f(x, y) * g(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(p, q) \cdot g(x-p, y-q) dpdq = F^{-1}(F(f(x, y)) \cdot F(g(x, y))),$$

where F denotes the 2-dimensional Fourier transform, and F^{-1} denotes the inverse 2-dimensional Fourier transform.

• **differentiation** [CLPP]:

$$\frac{\partial^n}{\partial x^n} \frac{\partial^m}{\partial y^m} f(x, y) = F^{-1}[(iu)^n (iv)^m F(f(x, y))].$$

In particular, we have the Laplacian operator:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f(x, y)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 f(x, y)}{\partial y^2} = F^{-1}[-(u^2 + v^2) \cdot F(f(x, y))].$$

• **full thresholding**:

$$g(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_a^A(f(x, y)) = \begin{cases} A, & \text{if } f(x, y) \geq a; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Indeed, we can obtain the required function by the following sequence of transformations:

Step 1. $f_1(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_a(f(x, y));$

Step 2. $f_2(x, y) = I_{max} - f_1(x, y);$

Step 3. $f_3(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_{I_{max}-a}(f_2(x, y));$

Step 4. $f_4(x, y) = I_{max} - f_3(x, y);$

Step 5. $g(x, y) = \frac{A}{I_{max}} \times f_4(x, y).$

It is possible to link an optical computer with an electronic one. In this case two additional elementary operations are required:

- $input_D(x, y)$;
- $output_D(x, y, f)$, where D is the label of the optical frame (SLM).

The first operation reads the value of function $f(x, y)$ at point (x, y) of the optical frame into the memory of the electronic computer; the second “writes” the value f from the memory to a point (x, y) on an optical frame (see e.g. [F]).

1.1.3 Discrete model of computation

This model is obtained by replacing bivariate functions and integrals of the previous model by 2-dimensional matrices and sums respectively. So, our set of elementary optical operations becomes as follows:

- **addition/subtraction:** $C(n, m) = A(n, m) \pm B(n, m)$ of two images in parallel for every (n, m) in a given range.
- **scalar multiplication:** $C(n, m) = k \cdot B(n, m)$ which is obtained as a result of the passage of light through both the SLM containing $B(n, m)$ and the SLM whose pixels have optical density k .
- **pixelwise multiplication:** $C(n, m) = A(n, m) \cdot B(n, m)$ in parallel for every (n, m) in a given range.
- **filtering (thresholding) of an image at a given level L :**

$$C(n, m) = \text{Threshold}_L(B(n, m)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } B(n, m) \geq L; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

- **difference operators:**

$$DA_x(n, m) = A(n + 1, m) - A(n, m);$$

$$DA_y(n, m) = A(n, m + 1) - A(n, m).$$

These operators play the role of spatial derivatives in the continuous model.

- **matrix–vector multiplication:**

$$B(n, m) = \sum_{k=1}^N A(n, k) \cdot V(k);$$

(see, for example, [RO], [YC]).

- **matrix–matrix multiplication:**

$$C(n, m) = \sum_{k=1}^N A(n, k) \cdot B(k, m);$$

(see, for example, [CKY], [HY], [GCY], [FFL]).

- **discrete Fourier transform:**

$$B(n, m) = \sum_{p=1}^N \sum_{q=1}^N A(p, q) \cdot e^{-\frac{2\pi i}{N}(pn+qm)};$$

(see, for example [G]).

- **convolution:**

$$C(n, m) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M A(n-i, m-j) \cdot B(i, j) = A(n, m) * B(n, m);$$

- **correlation:**

$$C(n, m) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M A(i+n, j+m) \cdot B(i, j) = A(n, m) \odot B(n, m);$$

1.1.4 Optical model of computation in terms of set theory

The continuous model of computation deals with arbitrary bivariate functions. We can specialize the operations given above to certain specific types of such functions. In particular, we can consider optical computations on characteristic functions of planar figures. Then some of the optical operations described above can be expressed in terms of set theory.

For example, the relationship

$$1_{A \cap B}(x, y) = 1_A(x, y) \cdot 1_B(x, y)$$

shows that constructing intersection of planar figures is a special case of multiplying two functions and, hence,

- $A \cap B$ is a primitive operation in optical computing;

Analogously, the following set theoretical operations can be considered as primitive in our model of computation:

- $A \cup B$: this follows from the relationship

$$1_{A \cup B}(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_0^1[1_A(x, y) + 1_B(x, y)];$$

- $A \setminus B$, based on the relationship

$$1_{A \setminus B}(x, y) = 1_A(x, y) - [1_A(x, y) \cdot 1_B(x, y)];$$

- **the complement A^c of set A** , based on the relationship

$$1_{A^c}(x, y) = 1_{\mathfrak{R}^2} - 1_A(x, y),$$

where the binary distribution $1_{\mathfrak{R}^2}$ is assumed to be prestored in optical memory as an item of the library of standard distributions (or standard binary masks);

•**extracting the boundary ∂A of figure A** : This follows from the relationship

$$\frac{\partial 1_A(x, y)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial 1_A(x, y)}{\partial y} = \begin{cases} \delta_{x,y}, & \text{if } (x, y) \in \partial A; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

showing that spatial differentiation of the image of figure A (which is primitive optical operation in the continuous model) gives rise to eliminating its interior and enhancing its boundary;

•**semi-conformal coordinate transformations of a figure**; same as for any 2-dimensional image.

The above operations are feasible not only in the continuous model of optical computation but also in the discrete one. For this we should replace characteristic functions by *characteristic matrices*:

$$1_A(n, m) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if pixel}(n, m) \in A; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and make use of difference operators for extracting the boundary of a pixelwise image rather than spatial differentiation.

Thus, this restricted optical computational model can be applied both to continuous and to discrete images.

1.1.5 Optical model of computation in terms of logic

Binary matrices of the previous section can be interpreted also as 2-dimensional boolean matrices. This allows optical operations on them to be expressed in terms of logical operations. In particular, the following pointwise boolean operations can be considered as elementary optical operations:

- $A(i, j) \& B(i, j)$;
- $A(i, j) \vee B(i, j)$;
- $\neg A(i, j)$;
- $A(i, j) \text{ XOR } B(i, j)$;
- $A(i, j) \text{ NAND } B(i, j)$;
- $A(i, j) \text{ NOR } B(i, j)$;
- $A(i, j) \text{ XNOR } B(i, j)$.

1.2 On Implementation of Optical Computational Models

To implement the models proposed above, we need an optical computer having at least the following capabilities:

- It can perform any sequence of the operations mentioned above.
- It can feed in constant time the results of operations already performed as input to operations that follow, i.e. it has constant-time feedback.

- It can store and retrieve in constant time frames from optical memory.

Even though feasibility of optical feedback has already been demonstrated [AAL], and the capacity of optical storage is getting progressively larger and nowadays can already achieve 750 images per crystal [STM], at present there exists no optical computer capable of performing every operation of either of the above models. Nevertheless, there exist various special-purpose optical computers capable of running algorithms comprising some of these operations. These computers can be classified into the following types:

- **optical pattern classifiers (recognizers) and learning machines**, based on matched filter optical correlators [MMK, CP, RS].
- **optical linear algebra processors (OLAP) and matrix processors**, capable of performing various matrix operations and solve systems of linear equations [CA, A, CK].
- **optical neural processors**, based mainly on performing matrix operations and thresholding and intended primarily for solving various optimization problems (including pattern recognition and machine learning) [P].
- **optical interconnection networks and communication processors**, utilizing optical matrix computations, optical coordinate transformations by computer generated holograms, thresholding operation, etc. [MG, SHC].
- **optical image processors**, based on performing correlation/convolution, thresholding and other auxiliary operations and capable of performing miscellaneous image processing tasks: substitute all occurrences of one pattern in the image by another pattern (termed symbolic substitution), perform median filtering of an image, skeletonization and edge detection, etc.; see [CKa, EZL, BC].
- **optical database/knowledgebase processors** mainly based on performing optical comparisons and thresholding operations [BBCCLS, Mi, MB, BGMMG]
- **optical symbolic processors**, aimed at performing various symbolic computations: manipulating data structures such as trees, lists, etc., [HA]; graphs and expressions reduction [GD]; polynomial processing [LCS]; inferences generation [ITI].
- **optical logic array processors**, which can perform thresholding and various logic operations (AND, OR, XOR, etc.) on data arrays [TI],[GB].
- **optical cellular automata** [TWCDG], which are 2-dimensional arrays of processing elements (PE) where each PE works on the corresponding pixel of a 2-dimensional binary array and is interconnected with its nearest neighbors. Optical cellular automata utilizes three base operations: routing 2-dimensional data from one processing plane to another (i.e. performing a special case of coordinate transformation); shift 2-dimensional data in either lateral direction by one pixel (also a special case of coordinate transformation) and performing 2-dimensional logic operations.

Tremendous efforts have been also applied to design digital optical computers [Mu], [Mc], which resulted recently in creating the first prototypes of such computers [Hu], [MFHJF]. However, digital optical computers, in our opinion, cannot fully utilize the inherent massive parallelism of the above computational models. Besides, many problems do not require high accuracy of computation provided by digital computers. Therefore, it is prudent, in our opinion, to develop optical computational geometry intended for general purpose analog or

hybrid optical computers which we believe will be created in the not so distant future.

Chapter 2

Basic Computations Involving Convolution

2.1 The Power of the δ -Function

A point source of light is a corner stone of many computational tricks in optical computational geometry. Its intensity distribution is described with the help of the δ -function:

$$\delta_{a,b}(x, y) = \begin{cases} \infty, & \text{if } x = a, y = b; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

satisfying the following relationship

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta_{a,b}(x, y) dx dy = 1.$$

The following properties of the δ -function are important for us:

•shifting property of the δ -function:

Convolution of any distribution $f(x, y)$ with $\delta_{a,b}(x, y)$ results in shifting the distribution by the vector (a, b) :

$$f(x, y) * \delta_{a,b}(x, y) = f(x - a, y - b).$$

Thus, we can shift a figure A by any vector optically in constant time by convolving the figure with the corresponding δ -function.

•duplicating property of the δ -function:

Convolution of a plane image $f(x, y)$ with a sum of point sources of light $\sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{a_i, b_i}$ results in duplication of the image into N copies, located at sites (a_i, b_i) ($i = \overline{1, N}$) respectively:

$$f(x, y) * \sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{a_i, b_i}(x, y) = \sum_{i=1}^N f(x - a_i, y - b_i).$$

Thus, transforming a frame containing a figure into the frame containing several copies of the same figure placed at prescribed sites $\{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ can be done optically in constant time.

This property gives rise to a fairly simple optical algorithm for constructing the Minkowski sum of plane figures.

2.1.1 Constant-time algorithm for computing Minkowski sums and its simplest applications

Let A and B be two planar figures, available on two input optical frames, and our goal is to produce their Minkowski sum

$$A + B = \{p + q | p \in A, q \in B\} = \bigcup_{p \in A} (B + p)$$

on an output frame. This can be done optically as follows:

Step 1. Amplify the intensity of each point of figure A up to the δ -function threshold. As a result we obtain the intensity distribution

$$\sum_{p \in A} \delta_p(x, y).$$

Step 2. Convolve this distribution with figure B (i.e. with the characteristic function $1_B(x, y)$). As a result, we obtain the following distribution:

$$\sum_{p \in A} 1_B(x - p_x, y - p_y) = \sum_{p \in A} 1_{B+p}(x, y),$$

where p_x and p_y are the coordinates of point p . It is easily seen that this distribution has the same domain of definition as the characteristic function of the figure

$$\bigcup_{p \in A} (B + p).$$

Thus, having thresholded the former image at intensity level 1, we will obtain the desired $1_{A+B}(x, y)$. This is reflected in the following step:

Step 3. Compute

$$1_{A+B}(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_0^1 \left[\sum_{p \in A} 1_{B+p}(x, y) \right].$$

The algorithm proposed can be expressed by the single formula:

$$1_{A+B}(x, y) = \text{Threshold}_0^1 [1_A(x, y) * \text{Threshold}_0^\delta(1_B(x, y))].$$

Thus, we obtain

Theorem 2.1.1 *The Minkowski sum of two plane figures can be constructed optically in constant time.*

This fact in itself already gives rise to fairly simple solutions to rather complicated problems of computational geometry and computer graphics, like hidden lines removal and filling the interior of a figure.

2.1.2 Constant-time reconstruction of the interior of a figure

Extracting the boundary of a binary image as well as reconstructing the entire image from its boundary (i.e. filling its interior) are important problems of image processing and computer graphics.

The first problem is solved optically comparatively easily (see section 1.1.4). To solve the inverse problem – reconstructing the interior of an image from its boundary, we can proceed as follows:

Step 1. Construct the Minkowski sum of the boundary with the ray of unit intensity emanating from the origin of coordinates along the X-axis. The result is the image where each boundary point emanates its own ray in the positive x -direction:

Collinear rays are superimposed and their intensities are added at points of superposition. Obviously, the resulting intensity will be odd at the interior points and even at the exterior points except at points belonging to rays tangent to the boundary:

Since the union of these tangent rays constitutes a set of measure zero, we conclude that by filtering points of odd intensity from points of even intensity we obtain the desired interior (up to a set of measure zero, which is invisible in practice).

The filtering can be performed as follows:

Step 2. Let $odd_even(x, y)$ be the intensity distribution obtained at Step 1. If we assume that unit intensity is equal to $\frac{\pi}{2a}$, where a is the parameter of the sine-transform (see section 1.1.2), then

$$\sin(a \cdot odd_even(x, y)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } odd_even(x, y) = odd; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Thus, having performed sine-transform of the distribution, we obtain the characteristic function of the portion of the image which has odd intensity. And this part is the desired interior of the figure, up to a set of measure zero.

Since computing both the Minkowski sum at Step 1 and performing sine-transform at Step 2 requires $O(1)$ optical steps, we obtain

Theorem 2.1.2 *The interior of a plane figure can be filled, up to a set of a few separate straight lines, optically in constant time.*

As mentioned above, detectors are not capable to distinguish sets of measure zero. Hence, this algorithm is satisfactory in practice. However, later on we will propose an alternative filling algorithm satisfactory even from the mathematical point of view, which tackles the problem of tangent rays and performs exact filling of the interior.

2.1.3 Hidden lines removal

Let L be a curve given on an input SLM. To remove its hidden parts which are invisible from $x = -\infty$, we can proceed as follows:

Step 1. Construct $L + ray$, where ray is the binary image storing the positive half of the x -axis:

Step 2. Compute $Threshold_1(L + ray)$, thereby obtaining the portion of this image which has intensity 1:

In the sum $L + ray$, the invisible portions of L have at least intensity 2; thus the visible part can be constructed as follows:

Step 3. Compute

$$Visible_part_of_L = L \cap Threshold_1(L + ray).$$

Thus, we obtain:

Lemma 2.1.3 *The portions of a curve that are visible from $x = -\infty$ can be constructed optically in constant time.*

2.2 The Power of the Log-Polar Mapping

Recall that the log-polar mapping is defined by:

$$\begin{cases} u = \ln \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}; \\ v = \tan^{-1}(\frac{y}{x}). \end{cases}$$

The power of the log-polar mapping is expressed in its ability to convert converging segments emanating from the origin of cartesian coordinates into non-converging parallel lines in log-polar coordinates. Such a set of parallel lines can be obtained from a single line by convolving it with a sum of δ - functions. Thus the log-polar mapping gives us a method for duplicating an image in non-parallel fashion. It results in several fairly simple algorithms, useful in optical computer graphics, which follow.

2.2.1 Visibility from a finite point

Visibility from a finite point can be reduced to the problem of visibility from infinity by applying the log-polar mapping, as follows.

Step 1. Move the origin of coordinates to that point P from which the visibility should be computed. It can be performed by computing the Minkowski difference of an input image and this point.

Step 2. Perform the log-polar mapping of the image obtained. As a result, the point P is mapped into the point at infinity and, hence, we can solve the visibility problem for it by applying the algorithm from the previous section.

Step 3. Construct the portions of the log-polar transformed curve that are visible from $u = -\infty$.

Step 4. Return back from log-polar to cartesian coordinates. As a result, the portions of the transformed curve that are visible from $u = -\infty$ in log-polar coordinates are transformed to those portions of the original curve which are visible from P in cartesian coordinates.

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 2.2.1 *The portion of a curve visible from either a finite point or from a point at infinity can be constructed optically in constant time. Also in constant time one can construct the visibility map of a polygon from a vertex or from an interior point.*

2.2.2 Simultaneous drawing of segments connecting the origin of coordinates with a given point set

One can easily note that in optical computational geometry we draw the solution of a problem on an SLM rather than “compute” it in the standard sense. Therefore, optical drawing of various geometrical figures is an essential part of optical computational geometry. Furthermore, although conventional computational geometry is a basis of standard computer graphics, this is not the case in optical computational geometry which is conversely based on graphical drawing of figures. This is why we present here several basic algorithms of optical computer graphics, to be used as tools in solving other problems in computational geometry.

We begin with the following problem of drawing straight line segments. Let a point set $P = \{P_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be given. We want to draw in parallel all segments connecting these points with the origin of coordinates. To perform it, we can proceed as follows:

Step 1. Change from cartesian coordinates to log-polar coordinates. As a result, the point set P is converted into another point set $Q = \{Q_i\}$.

Step 2. Construct the Minkowski difference $Q - ray$, where ray is defined in Section 2.1.

The image obtained consists of all rays emanating from points Q in the negative $(\ln R)$ -direction.

Step 3. Return from log-polar back to cartesian coordinates. The previous rays are converted into the desired segments:

Thus, we obtain

Lemma 2.2.2 *All straight line segments connecting a given point set with the origin of coordinates can be drawn optically in constant time.*

2.2.3 Drawing the sector between the origin and a curve

It is easily seen that if the point set P represents a continuous curve L , the segments connecting points of the curve with the origin of coordinates, whose union constitutes the sector of the curve, can all be drawn in constant optical time. Hence, optically we can draw a sector of an arbitrary curve in constant time:

Figure 2.1: The sector of a curve

2.2.4 The simplest optical convex hull algorithm

In constant optical time we can draw not only segments connecting the origin of coordinates with a point set or with a curve, but also draw all segments connecting such a point set with any other fixed point p (first shift the image so that p moves to the origin, and then apply the above technique). This gives rise to the simplest optical algorithm for constructing the convex hull of a given finite point set $P = \{P_i\}_{i=1}^N$:

Step 1. Move the origin of coordinates to point P_1 .

Step 2. Connect P_1 with all other points P_2, \dots, P_N . Denote the image obtained as $\overline{CH_1}$.

For $i = 2$ to $N - 1$ do;

Step $(2 \cdot i - 1)$. Move the origin of coordinates to point P_i .

Step $(2 \cdot i)$. Connect P_i with $\overline{CH_{i-1}}$. Denote the image obtained as $\overline{CH_i}$.

End For;

It is obvious that $\overline{CH_N}$ is the convex hull of P . Thus, this algorithm constructs the convex hull of a finite point set in linear time.

The following figures show the flow of the algorithm for an input set of four points:

Figure 2.2: The image obtained after the first step of the algorithm

Figure 2.3: The result of the second step of the algorithm

Figure 2.4: The result of the third step of the algorithm

2.3 How to Represent a Complex Image as a Convolution of a Simple One with a Sum of Point Sources

In what follows we often will face the need to construct in constant time a complex image

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = 0\}$$

consisting of many similar (but not identical) images $\{(x, y) | f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = 0\}$. We know that, if $f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = g(x - a_i, y - b_i)$, then such a complex image can be obtained from $\{(x, y) | g(x, y) = 0\}$ by its convolution with the sum of point sources $\sum_{i=1}^N \delta_{a_i, b_i}$.

However, we can also handle more complex situations.

Suppose, that

$$\{(x, y) | f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = 0\} = \{(x, y) | g(u_1(x, y) - u_2(a_i, b_i), v_1(x, y) - v_2(a_i, b_i)) = 0\}.$$

If such a representation is possible, then we can construct the complex image in constant time as follows:

Step 1. Perform the coordinate transformation

$$\begin{cases} p = u_2(x, y) \\ q = v_2(x, y) \end{cases}$$

on the image $\{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^N$. As a result we obtain a new point image $\{(p_i, q_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where $p_i = u_2(a_i, b_i)$, $q_i = v_2(a_i, b_i)$. (We assume that this transformation is semi-conformal, or else that it can be performed by a constant number of semi-conformal transformations, which is almost always the case in practice.)

Step 2. Compute the Minkowski sum

$$\{(p_i, q_i)\}_{i=1}^N + \{(s, t) | g(s, t) = 0\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(s, t) | g(s - p_i, t - q_i) = 0\}.$$

Step 3. Change from (s, t) coordinates to (x, y) coordinates by the transformation (again, assuming semi-conformality):

$$\begin{cases} s = u_1(x, y) \\ t = v_1(x, y). \end{cases}$$

As a result, the image

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(s, t) | g(s - p_i, t - q_i) = 0\}$$

is transformed into the desired image

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | g(u_1(x, y) - u_2(a_i, b_i), v_1(x, y) - v_2(a_i, b_i)) = 0\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = 0\}.$$

Remark: To perform this step one needs to invert the above relationship between (s, t) and (x, y) , i.e. to express (x, y) in terms of (s, t) . If this is impossible, one can still resort to additional tricks (described below).

We demonstrate this technique on the following simple example.

2.3.1 An optical algorithm for “radii-to-rings” mapping

Let a set of points $\{(R_i, R_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ be given; we want to transform this point set into the set of rings $\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | x^2 + y^2 = R_i^2\}$, i.e. perform a “radii-to-rings” transformation.

In this case $f(x, y, a_i, b_i) = f(x, y, R_i, R_i) = x^2 + y^2 - R_i^2$.

Since,

$$\{(x, y) | x^2 + y^2 - R_i^2 = 0\} = \{(x, y) | e^{2(\ln(x \cdot \text{sgn}(x)) - \ln R_i)} + e^{2(\ln(y \cdot \text{sgn}(y)) - \ln R_i)} - 1 = 0\},$$

we can put

$$g(s, t) = e^{2s} + e^{2t} - 1,$$

and

$$\begin{cases} s = u_1(x, y) = \ln(x \cdot \operatorname{sgn}(x)) \\ t = v_1(x, y) = \ln(y \cdot \operatorname{sgn}(y)) \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_2(R_i, R_i) = \ln R_i \\ v_2(R_i, R_i) = \ln R_i \end{cases}$$

However, (x, y) cannot be expressed uniquely in terms of (s, t) over the entire plane, but only for each quadrant of the plane separately.

Hence, we can make use the algorithm just described for transforming point set $\{(R_i, R_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ into quarter-rings, e.g. in the quadrant $x \geq 0, y \geq 0$.

It looks as follows:

Step 1. Perform the pointwise transformation

$$\{(R_i, R_i)\}_{i=1}^N \longrightarrow \{(\ln R_i, \ln R_i)\}_{i=1}^N,$$

(see Fig. 2.5).

Step 2. Assuming that the binary mask of the image $\{(s, t) | e^{2s} + e^{2t} - 1 = 0\}$ (see Fig. 2.6) is prestored in the optical memory as a standard mask, compute the Minkowski sum

$$\begin{aligned} & \{(\ln R_i, \ln R_i)\}_{i=1}^N + \{(s, t) | e^{2s} + e^{2t} - 1 = 0\} = \\ & = \bigcup \{(s, t) | e^{2(s - \ln R_i)} + e^{2(t - \ln R_i)} - 1 = 0\}, \end{aligned}$$

(see Fig. 2.7)

Step 3. Return from (s, t) to (x, y) coordinates by the following pointwise transformation:

$$\begin{cases} x = e^s \\ y = e^t \end{cases}.$$

As a result we obtain the desired quarter-rings (see Fig. 2.8).

We can now reflect the quarter-rings with respect to the coordinate axes, and obtain the missing parts of the rings (see Fig. 2.9). Note that it is more natural to start the above algorithm with an input image of the form $\{(R_i, 0)\}_{i=1}^N$. To transform this set to the diagonal set $\{(R_i, R_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, we need a few more optical steps. We will describe them in section 4.1 below.

Thus, we obtain

Lemma 2.3.1 *The above point-to-ring transformation can be performed optically in constant time.*

The chapters that follow contain many other examples of using the above trick.

Figure 2.5: Image $\{(\ln R_i, \ln R_i)\}_{i=1}^2$, where $R_1 = 1, R_2 = 2$

Figure 2.6: Binary mask of the image $\{(s, t) | e^{2s} + e^{2t} - 1 = 0\}$

Figure 2.7: Image $\cup\{(s, t) | e^{2(s-\ln R_i)} + e^{2(t-\ln R_i)} - 1 = 0\}$

Figure 2.8: Quarter-rings as a final result of the algorithm

Figure 2.9: Reflection of the quarter-rings obtained with respect to coordinate axes and entire rings as their union

Chapter 3

Optical Computing in Parallel on a Single Optical Processor

Computing in parallel on electronic computers naturally requires at least two processors. Fortunately, this is not the case for optical computers. They may be designed to perform several elementary operations of the same type in parallel on a single optical processor. Thus we can obtain an SIMD (Single Instruction Multiple Data) optical computer with a single optical processor.

To see how this can be done, suppose that we want to perform the following pointwise multiplications:

$$\begin{cases} h_1(x, y) = f_1(x, y) \cdot g_1(x, y) \\ h_2(x, y) = f_2(x, y) \cdot g_2(x, y) \\ \dots \\ h_n(x, y) = f_n(x, y) \cdot g_n(x, y) \end{cases}$$

It is not necessary to use for this aim n optical processors. Instead, we can “mix” all the functions $f_i(x, y)$ by marking each $f_k(x, y)$ by a different color $f_k^{\lambda_k}(x, y)$, where λ_k is a specific wave-length of radiation representing $f_k(x, y)$ and $g_k(x, y)$, which is handled similarly. We form the *polychromatic waves* $\sum f_k^{\lambda_k}$ and $\sum g_k^{\lambda_k}$ using a chromatic multiplexor [CKY], and then apply to them any operation of the optical computational models, observing that waves of different color do not influence each other. This means that $f_i^{\lambda_i} \odot g_j^{\lambda_j} = 0$ if $i \neq j$, where \odot is any of the above mentioned elementary operations. For example,

$$\sum_{k=1}^n f_k^{\lambda_k}(x, y) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n g_k^{\lambda_k}(x, y) = \sum_{k=1}^n (f_k^{\lambda_k}(x, y) \cdot g_k^{\lambda_k}(x, y)).$$

The resulting sum can then be decomposed into its monochromatic constituents by a chromatic demultiplexor [CKY].

Usually, polychromatic computation can be regarded as white light computation because, on one hand, white light is readily available and, on the other hand, it contains an infinite number of wave lengths. Thus, white light optical computer is in fact a computer with infinite number of virtual processors, making it a very powerful device indeed.

Of course there are drawbacks in using the polychromatic approach. It requires polychromatic SLM's and very high resolution of the chromatic multiplexors and demultiplexors, and it also requires other complicated optical devices which are still very imperfect with nowadays state of the art. For these reasons, in what follows we will prefer algorithms for optical computers which work in the monochromatic mode.

Nevertheless, in this chapter we consider the technique of parallelizing "monochromatic" optical algorithms having $O(N)$ time complexity into constant time "polychromatic" algorithms. This technique is demonstrated on the problem of reconstructing a polygonal image from its vertices.

3.1 Polygonal Image Reconstruction From Its Vertices

We have already mentioned that it is straightforward to perform operations such as $A \cup B$, $A \cap B$, $A + B$, etc., in an optical manner if the characteristic functions $1_A(x, y)$ and $1_B(x, y)$ of the polygons A, B are already stored on optical frames. However, in many applications we often know only the vertices of the polygons. Therefore the problem arises to compute the characteristic function of a polygon from its vertices, given in electronic memory in their cyclic order along the polygon boundary.

3.1.1 Reconstructing the boundary of a polygon from its vertices

Let the set of vertices $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of a polygon be given. To reconstruct its boundary, we can draw all segments $\overline{A_i A_{i+1}}$ one by one on some frame SLM_1 and transfer each time a new segment from SLM_1 to another frame SLM_2 where finally all segments will be accumulated to form the desired boundary. Drawing a segment can be performed by the algorithm of section 2.2.2 for drawing segments connecting the origin of coordinates with a given set of points which, in this case is just a singleton point.

Thus, our algorithm for reconstructing the boundary of a polygon from its vertices is as follows:

Step 1. Set

$$SLM_1 = \emptyset;$$

$$SLM_2 = \emptyset,$$

i.e. clear the SLMs.

For $i = 1$ *to* $N - 1$ *do*;

Step $(5 \cdot i - 4)$. Compute

$$SLM_3 = A_i;$$

$$SLM_1 = \{A_i, A_{i+1}\},$$

i.e. write vertex A_i on SLM_3 and vertices A_i, A_{i+1} on SLM_1 . (Here vertices are transferred from optical memory.)

Step (5 · i - 3). Compute The Minkowski difference

$$SLM_1 = SLM_1 - SLM_3 = \{O, (A_{i+1} - A_i)\},$$

where O denotes the origin of coordinates.

Step (5 · i - 2). Draw on SLM_1 the segment $\overline{O(A_{i+1} - A_i)}$ using the algorithm from section 2.2.2.

Step (5 · i - 1). Compute the Minkowski sum

$$SLM_1 = SLM_1 + SLM_3 = \overline{O(A_{i+1} - A_i)} + A_i = \overline{A_i A_{i+1}}.$$

Step 5 · i. Compute

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 \cup SLM_1 = \bigcup_{k=1}^i \overline{A_k A_{k+1}}.$$

End For;

Obviously, the time complexity of the algorithm is $O(N)$. However, we can parallelize it using polychromatic coding of the vertices to facilitate the computation in parallel.

Let F^λ denote, for any figure F , either the amplitude $1_F(x, y)$ of a plane light wave of wavelength λ , or the transmittance $1_F(x, y)$ of an optical frame (a filter) for this wavelength (for other wavelengths transmittance is assumed to be zero).

Using these notations we obtain the following algorithm for constructing the boundary ∂P of any polygon P from its vertices $\{A_i\}$. It is supposed in this algorithm that any vertex A_i is represented bichromatically: as $A_i^{\lambda_i}$ on one frame SLM_1 and as $A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}$ on another frame SLM_2 respectively (where $\lambda_0 = \lambda_N$). (We still have a serial bottleneck of preparing these two SLM's, but it is a much shorter operation than the preceding serial algorithm.) The algorithm is an easy generalization of the preceding one, and works as follows:

Step 1. Compute

$$SLM_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_i},$$

$$SLM_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}.$$

(This is the only serial step.)

Step 2. Compute

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 \cup SLM_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (A_i^{\lambda_i} \cup A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}).$$

Step 3. Compute the Minkowski difference

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 - SLM_1 = \left[\bigcup_{i=1}^N O^{\lambda_{i-1}} \right] \bigcup \left[\bigcup_{i=1}^N (A_i - A_{i-1})^{\lambda_{i-1}} \right].$$

Step 4. Compute

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^N O^{\lambda_{i-1}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N P_i^{\lambda_{i-1}},$$

where $P_i^{\lambda_{i-1}} = (A_i - A_{i-1})^{\lambda_{i-1}}$.

Step 5. Transform SLM_2 from cartesian coordinates to log-polar coordinates, transforming each point $P_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}$ to another point $Q_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}$.

Step 6. Compute

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 - \bigcup_{i=1}^N ray^{\lambda_{i-1}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N Q_i^{\lambda_{i-1}} - \bigcup_{i=1}^N ray^{\lambda_{i-1}} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (Q_i^{\lambda_{i-1}} - ray^{\lambda_{i-1}}),$$

where $ray^{\lambda_{i-1}}$ is the positive half of the x -axis having color λ_{i-1} and $\bigcup_{i=1}^N ray^{\lambda_{i-1}}$ is the corresponding multicolor mask stored in the optical memory of the computer. The image obtained consists of parallel rays emanating from the points $\{Q_i\}$ and having colors $\{\lambda_{i-1}\}$ respectively.

Step 7. Return from log-polar coordinates back to cartesian coordinates. The previous rays on SLM_2 are converted into the union of segments

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \overline{OP_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}}.$$

Step 8. Compute the Minkowski sum

$$SLM_2 = SLM_2 + SLM_1 = \overline{OP_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}} + \{A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}\} = \{\overline{A_{i-1}A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}}}\}.$$

As a result we obtain the desired boundary where each segment, however, has its own color.

Step 9. Convert the color image obtained into a black-and-white image of the boundary by means of usual black-and-white photography where a photographic film is replaced by a black-and-white SLM.

Except for Step 1 that outputs the data vertices into the optical frames, this algorithm requires $O(1)$ optical operations. Note that the color scheme implicitly encodes the cyclic order of vertices along the polygon boundary.

Thus, we obtain

Theorem 3.1.1 *Let the vertices $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of a simple polygon P be given. Then we can reconstruct optically the boundary of P in $O(N)$ steps using a single optical processor which works in monochromatic mode or in $O(1)$ steps (excluding a linear-time input step), using a single processor which works in the polychromatic mode.*

3.1.2 Reconstruction of the interior of a polygon from its boundary

The preceding algorithm reconstructs all edges of the boundary of a polygon P , i.e. reconstructs ∂P . Next we want to construct P from ∂P . The algorithm that we propose is based on the following two simple lemmas.

Lemma 3.1.2 *For every simple polygon P we have:*

$$P = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{x \mid \exists y \in \partial P \quad (x \in \overline{A_i y} \subset P)\},$$

where $\{A_i\}_{i=1}^N$ is the set of vertices of the polygon P and ∂P denotes its boundary.

Proof. Let us denote $Q_i = \{x \mid \exists y \in \partial P \quad (x \in \overline{A_i y} \subset P)\}$. Q_i is actually the portion of P that is *visible* from A_i . Since every point of P is visible from at least one vertex, the claim follows. □

Next we replace the Cartesian coordinates by log-polar coordinates and make the center of polar coordinates at vertex A_i . As a result, the image Q_i is transformed into the image $Q_i - A_i$. Then we have:

Lemma 3.1.3

$$\text{log_polar_mapping_of}(Q_i - A_i) = \{(R, \theta) \mid \alpha_i \leq \theta \leq \beta_i; R \in \bigcap_{r \in \{\rho \mid f_i(\rho, \theta) = 1\}} (-\infty, r]\},$$

where α_i, β_i are the θ -coordinates of points $A_{i-1} - A_i$ and $A_{i+1} - A_i$, respectively, and $f_i(\rho, \theta)$ is the characteristic function of $\partial P - A_i$ in log-polar coordinates whose origin is located at the point A_i .

Proof. The lemma asserts the obvious fact that for a point $x \in P$ to be visible from A_i it is necessary and sufficient that the polar angle of x lie between the orientations of the two edges of P adjacent to A_i and that the distance from x to A_i does not exceed the distance from A_i to any point on ∂P with the same polar angle. □

It is easy to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(Q_i - A_i) &= \{(R, \theta) \mid \alpha_i \leq \theta \leq \beta_i \ ; \ R \in \bigcap_{r \in \{\rho \mid f_i(\rho, \theta) = 1\}} (-\infty, r]\} = \\ &= \mathfrak{R}^2 \setminus \{(R, \theta) \mid \theta < \alpha_i\} \setminus \{(R, \theta) \mid \theta > \beta_i\} \setminus \{(R, \theta) \mid R \in \bigcup_{r \in \{\rho \mid f_i(\rho, \theta) = 1\}} (r, \infty)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Note also that the rightmost set is simply the Minkowski sum

$$\text{log_polar_mapping_of}(\partial P - A_i) + \text{ray}$$

(where *ray* is the positive *x*-axis). This relationship gives us the following formula for *log_polar_mapping_of*($Q_i - A_i$):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(Q_i - A_i) = \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus [lower_half_plane + (0, \alpha_i)] \setminus \\ \setminus [upper_half_plane + (0, \beta_i)] \setminus [\text{log_polar_mapping_of}(\partial P - A_i) + ray], \end{aligned}$$

where

$$lower_half_plane = \{(R, \theta) | \theta \leq 0\},$$

$$upper_half_plane = \{(R, \theta) | \theta \geq 0\}.$$

Based on this formula we can offer the following algorithm for reconstructing a polygon P from its boundary (we suppose that ∂P is given).

Step 1. Set $P = \emptyset$.

For $i = 1$ *to* $N - 1$ *Do*;

Step 8 · $i - 7$. Compute $\partial P - A_i$, i.e. move the origin of coordinates into the point A_i .

Step 8 · $i - 6$. Compute *log_polar_mapping_of*($\partial P - A_i$).

Step 8 · $i - 5$. Compute

$$(R_i, \alpha_i) = \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(A_{i-1} - A_i);$$

$$(r_i, \beta_i) = \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(A_{i+1} - A_i).$$

Step 8 · $i - 4$. Perform coordinate transformations:

$$(R_i, \alpha_i) \longrightarrow (0, \alpha_i);$$

$$(r_i, \beta_i) \longrightarrow (0, \beta_i).$$

Step 8 · $i - 3$. Compute

$$\begin{aligned} \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(Q_i - A_i) = \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus [lower_half_plane + (0, \alpha_i)] \\ \setminus [upper_half_plane + (0, \beta_i)] \setminus [\text{log_polar_mapping_of}(\partial P - A_i) + ray]. \end{aligned}$$

Step 8 · $i - 2$. Return from log-polar coordinates back to cartesian coordinates. As a result, we obtain $Q_i - A_i$.

Step 8 · $i - 1$. Compute $Q_i = (Q_i - A_i) + A_i$.

Step 8 · i . Compute $P = P \cup Q_i$.

End For;

It is obvious that the complexity of this algorithm is $O(N)$. We can speed up this algorithm, using polychromatic encoding as in the previous subsection, and obtain an algorithm that requires $O(1)$ optical operations (excluding the output of the data on optical frames, given in Step 1 below). The parallelized version of the previous algorithm looks as follows:

Step 1. Compute

$$SLM_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \partial P^{\lambda_i};$$

$$SLM_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_i};$$

$$SLM_3 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_{i-1}};$$

$$SLM_4 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_{i+1}}.$$

(Note that SLM_2 and SLM_3 are already available from Step 1 of the polychromatic algorithm in Section 3.1.2; SLM_4 is similarly prepared.)

Step 2. Compute

$$SLM_5 = SLM_1 - SLM_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (\partial P^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i}).$$

Step 3. Transform SLM_5 from cartesian coordinates to log-polar coordinates, i.e. compute

$$SLM_5 = \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(SLM_5) = \text{log_polar_mapping_of}\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (\partial P^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i})\right).$$

Step 4. Compute

$$SLM_3 = SLM_3 - SLM_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (A_{i+1}^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i});$$

$$SLM_4 = SLM_2 - SLM_4 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (A_i^{\lambda_i} - A_{i-1}^{\lambda_i}).$$

Step 5. Transform SLM_3 and SLM_4 from cartesian to log-polar coordinates:

$$SLM_3 = \text{log_polar_mapping_of}(SLM_3) = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (R_i^{\lambda_i}, \beta_i^{\lambda_i});$$

$$SLM_4 = \log_polar_mapping_of(SLM_4) = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (r_i^{\lambda_i}, \alpha_i^{\lambda_i}).$$

Step 6. Project the images on both SLM_3 and SLM_4 onto the θ -axis:

$$SLM_3 = Pr_\theta(SLM_3) = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (0, \beta_i^{\lambda_i});$$

$$SLM_4 = Pr_\theta(SLM_4) = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (0, \alpha_i^{\lambda_i}).$$

Step 7. Compute

$$SLM_3 = SLM_3 + \bigcup_{i=1}^N upper_half_plane^{\lambda_i} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N [upper_half_plane^{\lambda_i} + (0, \beta_i^{\lambda_i})];$$

$$SLM_4 = SLM_4 + \bigcup_{i=1}^N lower_half_plane^{\lambda_i} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N [lower_half_plane^{\lambda_i} + (0, \alpha_i^{\lambda_i})].$$

Here $\bigcup_{i=1}^N upper_half_plane^{\lambda_i}$ is a multicolor image of the upper half plane, stored as a mask in the optical memory, and similarly for $\bigcup_{i=1}^N lower_half_plane^{\lambda_i}$.

Step 8. Compute

$$SLM_5 = SLM_5 + \bigcup_{i=1}^N ray^{\lambda_i} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N [\log_polar_mapping_of(\partial P^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i}) + ray^{\lambda_i}].$$

Step 9. Compute

$$SLM_1 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (\mathbb{R}^2)^{\lambda_i} \setminus SLM_3 \setminus SLM_4 \setminus SLM_5 = \log_polar_mapping_of\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^N Q_i^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i}\right).$$

Step 10. Transform SLM_1 from log-polar to cartesian coordinates. As a result, we obtain on SLM_1 the following image:

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N (Q_i^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i}).$$

Step 11. Compute the final result

$$SLM_1 = SLM_1 + SLM_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (Q_i^{\lambda_i} - A_i^{\lambda_i}) + \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i^{\lambda_i} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N Q_i^{\lambda_i}.$$

Step 12. Convert the multicolor image obtained into the black-and-white image of the interior of a polygon.

Hence we obtain:

Theorem 3.1.4 *Reconstruction of a simple polygon from its sequence of vertices requires $O(N)$ elementary optical operations in the monochromatic mode and $O(1)$ operations in the polychromatic mode (the latter bound excludes a preliminary output step into optical frames from electronic storage).*

Clearly, if P is convex then it suffices to connect one fixed vertex with all points on ∂P . Hence we obtain:

Theorem 3.1.5 *Reconstruction of a convex polygon from its boundary requires $O(1)$ elementary optical operations, even in the monochromatic mode.*

In analogous manner we can parallelize any optical SIMD algorithms like the simplest convex hull algorithm from section 2.2.4 or the Voronoi diagram algorithm given later in section 5.14.

Chapter 4

Optical Realization of Geometric Duality

4.1 Mapping Straight Lines to Their Dual Points

Dual transitions from straight lines $\{(x, y) | a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y = 1\}_{i=1}^N$ to their dual points $\{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ and back are very useful techniques in standard computational geometry. Therefore, their optical realizations are among the primary tasks of optical computational geometry.

Fortunately, optics allows us to perform something similar to this in a single step. We refer to the Hough transform, which is a primitive optical operation in our model of computation, and which maps straight lines $\{(x, y) | a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y = 1\}_{i=1}^N$, or segments contained in such lines, into points $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where

$$p_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a_i^2 + b_i^2}}, \quad \theta_i = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{b_i}{a_i}\right).$$

Thus, to complete the desired straight-line-to-dual-point transform, it only remains to perform the following coordinate transformation

$$(p, \theta) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{p}, \frac{\sin \theta}{p}\right) = (a, b).$$

Unfortunately, this transformation is not semi-conformal:

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial \theta} \neq \frac{\partial b}{\partial p}$$

and, hence, cannot be performed in a single step, as above. Therefore, to perform it we use a round-about way. First, perform the partial transformations, each of which is semi-conformal:

$$(p, \theta) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{p}, -(\ln p) \sin \theta\right) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{p}, 0\right)$$

and

$$(p, \theta) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{p^2}, \frac{\sin \theta}{p} \right) \longrightarrow \left(0, \frac{\sin \theta}{p} \right).$$

As a result, we obtain two images (see Fig. 4.1):

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, 0 \right) \right\}_{i=1}^N \quad \text{and} \quad \left\{ \left(0, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^N.$$

Figure 4.1: Images $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^4$, $\{(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, 0)\}_{i=1}^4$ and $\{(0, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i})\}_{i=1}^4$ respectively.

We then compute the Minkowski sum of these images

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, 0 \right) \right\}_{i=1}^N + \left\{ \left(0, \frac{\sin \theta_j}{p_j} \right) \right\}_{j=1}^N = \left\{ \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_j}{p_j} \right) \right\}_{i,j=1}^N,$$

using the algorithm described in the previous chapter (see Fig. 4.2).

Figure 4.2: The Minkowski sum $\{(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, 0)\}_{i=1}^4 + \{(0, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i})\}_{i=1}^4 = \{(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_j}{p_j})\}_{i,j=1}^4$.

Finally, we obtain the desired image by the operation (see Fig. 4.3):

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^N = \left\{ \left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_j}{p_j} \right) \right\}_{i,j=1}^N \cap \bigcup_{i=1}^N \left\{ (x, y) \mid \frac{x^2}{p_i^2} + \frac{y^2}{p_i^2} = 1 \right\},$$

Figure 4.3: Dual points $\{(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i})\}$ as a result of the operation $\{(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_j}{p_j})\} \cap \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | x^2 + y^2 = p_i^2\}$.

To perform the last operation we need the image $\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | x^2 + y^2 = p_i^2\}$. If we have the point set $\{(p_i, p_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, available on an optical frame, then we can convert these points into the above rings, using the algorithm given in section 2.3.1. However, we have the point set $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ and to convert it into the set $\{(p_i, p_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ we apply the following simple algorithm:

Step 1. Perform the pointwise coordinate transformation

$$\{(p_i, \theta_i)\} \longrightarrow \{(p_i, 0)\}$$

(see Fig. 4.4).

Figure 4.4: Images $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}$, $\{(p_i, 0)\}$, and $\{(0, p_i)\}$, respectively.

Step 2. Perform coordinate transformation

$$\{(p_i, 0)\} \longrightarrow \{(0, p_i)\}$$

(see Fig. 4.4).

Step 3. Compute the Minkowski sum

$$\{(p_i, 0)\} + \{(0, p_j)\} = \{(p_i, p_j)\}$$

(see Fig. 4.5).

Figure 4.5: Minkowski sum $\{(p_i, p_j)\} = \{(p_i, 0)\} + \{(0, p_j)\}$.

Step 4. Construct the final image as follows:

$$\{(p_i, p_i)\} = \{(p_i, p_j)\} \cap \{(x, y) | x = y\},$$

where the the binary mask of the image $\{(x, y) | x = y\}$ is assumed to be stored in the optical memory in the library of standard masks (see Fig. 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Desired image $\{(p_i, p_i)\}$ as a result of the operation $\{(p_i, p_j)\} \cap \text{line}(x = y)$.

Thus, we obtain

Theorem 4.1.1 *A set of lines $\{xa_i + yb_i = 1\}_{i=1}^N$ can be mapped into their dual points $\{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in monochromatic mode.*

4.2 Mapping Points to Their Dual Lines

Suppose next that we are given a point image $P = \{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ on a SLM, and we want to transform it into the dual line image $\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y = 1\}$.

Even though this can be performed optically in a single step by a matrix of holograms [ALTF], because of the remark in section 1.1.2, we prefer to propose another approach for doing so, which avoids the use of such a matrix of holograms and is based instead on the algorithm for generating a complex image described in section 2.3.

This means that we should represent $a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y = 1$ as a convolution $f[s(x, y), t(x, y)] * \delta_{u(a_i, b_i), v(a_i, b_i)}$, where convolution is performed with respect to the (s, t) variables.

Unfortunately, we failed to find such a representation for any (x, y) and (a_i, b_i) . That is why we decided to subdivide the xy -plane and the ab -plane into several regions and to find the desired expression for each combination of the regions. For example, if we assume that $y > 0$ and $a_i \cdot b_i > 0$, then the desired expression can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y - 1 &= a_i \cdot \left[\left(x - \frac{1}{a_i}\right) + y \cdot \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right] = \\ a_i \cdot \left[\left(x - \frac{1}{a_i}\right) + e^{(\ln y + \ln \frac{b_i}{a_i})} \right] &= a_i \cdot \left[(s + e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}} \right], \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} s = x \\ t = \ln y. \end{cases}$$

Thus, since we can divide by a_i without changing the line itself, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{a_i} [a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y - 1] = (s + e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}}.$$

Hence, if $y > 0$ and $a_i \cdot b_i > 0$, then

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y - 1 = 0\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N \{(x, y) | x = s, y = e^t, (s + e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}} = 0\}.$$

This relationship can be generalized, to cover all possibilities, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \{(x, y) | a_i \cdot x + b_i \cdot y - 1 = 0\} = \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \{(x, y) | x = s, y = e^t, (s + e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}} = 0\}, & \text{if } y > 0 \quad \& \quad a_i \cdot b_i > 0; \\ \{(x, y) | x = s, y = -e^t, (s - e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i}} = 0\}, & \text{if } y < 0 \quad \& \quad a_i \cdot b_i > 0; \\ \{(x, y) | x = s, y = -e^t, (s + e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln(-\frac{b_i}{a_i})} = 0\}, & \text{if } y < 0 \quad \& \quad a_i \cdot b_i < 0; \\ \{(x, y) | x = s, y = e^t, (s - e^t) * \delta_{\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln(-\frac{b_i}{a_i})} = 0\}, & \text{if } y > 0 \quad \& \quad a_i \cdot b_i < 0; \\ \{(x, y) | y = \frac{1}{b_i}\}, & \text{if } a_i = 0; \\ \{(x, y) | x = \frac{1}{a_i}\}, & \text{if } b_i = 0. \end{array} \right. \quad (*) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we can propose the following algorithm for the points-to-dual-lines transformation:

Step 1. Divide the point image P into four subimages (see Fig. 4.7):

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i > 0} = P \cap \{(a, b) \mid a \cdot b > 0\};$$

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i < 0} = P \cap \{(a, b) \mid a \cdot b < 0\};$$

$$P_{a_i=0} = P \cap \{(a, b) \mid a = 0\};$$

$$P_{b_i=0} = P \cap \{(a, b) \mid b = 0\}.$$

We assume that, with no loss of generality,

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i > 0} = \{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=1}^{N_1};$$

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i < 0} = \{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2};$$

$$P_{a_i=0} = \{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=N_2+1}^{N_3};$$

$$P_{b_i=0} = \{(a_i, b_i)\}_{i=N_3+1}^{N_4}.$$

Otherwise, change indices of points to satisfy this condition.

Step 2. Perform the coordinate transformations (see Fig. 4.8):

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i > 0} \longrightarrow \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^{N_1};$$

$$P_{a_i \cdot b_i < 0} \longrightarrow \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \left(-\frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right) \right\}_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2};$$

$$P_{a_i=0} \longrightarrow \left\{ \left(0, \frac{1}{b_i} \right) \right\}_{i=N_2+1}^{N_3};$$

$$P_{b_i=0} \longrightarrow \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, 0 \right) \right\}_{i=N_3+1}^{N_4}.$$

The first two transformations are not semi-conformal, but we can still perform them by a constant number of semi-conformal transformations. For example, we obtain the first transformation by the chain

$$(a, b) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{b}{a}, -\ln \frac{1}{a} \right) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{b}{a}, \ln \frac{1}{a} \right) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{b}{a}, \frac{1}{a} \right) \longrightarrow \left(\ln \frac{b}{a}, \frac{1}{a} \right) \longrightarrow \left(\frac{1}{a}, \ln \frac{b}{a} \right).$$

An analogous chain can be derived for the second subimage of P .

Step 3. Compute the Minkowski sums:

$$\{(s, t) \mid s + e^t = 0\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^{N_1} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{N_1} \{(s, t) \mid \left(s - \frac{1}{a_i} \right) + e^{(t + \ln \frac{b_i}{a_i})} = 0\} = L_1(s, t),$$

(see Fig 4.9);

$$\{(s, t) \mid s - e^t = 0\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i} \right) \right\}_{i=1}^{N_1} = \bigcup_{i=1}^{N_1} \{(s, t) \mid \left(s - \frac{1}{a_i} \right) - e^{(t + \ln \frac{b_i}{a_i})} = 0\} = L_2(s, t),$$

(see Fig 4.10);

$$\{(s, t) \mid s + e^t = 0\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln\left(-\frac{b_i}{a_i}\right) \right) \right\}_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2} = \bigcup_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2} \{(s, t) \mid (s - \frac{1}{a_i}) + e^{(t + \ln(-\frac{b_i}{a_i}))} = 0\} = L_3(s, t),$$

(see Fig. 4.11);

$$\{(s, t) \mid s - e^t = 0\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln\left(-\frac{b_i}{a_i}\right) \right) \right\}_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2} = \bigcup_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2} \{(s, t) \mid (s - \frac{1}{a_i}) - e^{(t + \ln(-\frac{b_i}{a_i}))} = 0\} = L_4(s, t),$$

(see Fig. 4.12);

$$\{(s, t) \mid t = 0\} + \left\{ \left(0, \frac{1}{b_i} \right) \right\}_{i=N_2+1}^{N_3} = \bigcup_{i=N_2+1}^{N_3} \{(s, t) \mid t = \frac{1}{b_i}\} = L_5(s, t),$$

(see Fig. 4.13);

$$\{(s, t) \mid s = 0\} + \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{a_i}, 0 \right) \right\}_{i=N_3+1}^{N_4} = \bigcup_{i=N_3+1}^{N_4} \{(s, t) \mid s = \frac{1}{a_i}\} = L_6(s, t),$$

(see Fig. 4.14).

Step 4. Perform the coordinate transformation $x = s$, $y = e^t$ on images $L_1(s, t)$ and $L_4(s, t)$ and the coordinate transformation $x = s$, $y = -e^t$ on images $L_2(s, t)$ and $L_3(s, t)$.

As a result, we obtain all constituents of the right hand side of the relationship (*) (see Fig. 4.15).

Step 5. Combine the images obtained at Step 4 into the full lines dual to the point set P (see Fig. 4.16).

4.3 First Constant-Time Optical Convex Hull Algorithm

Geometric duality has many useful applications in computational geometry [CGL]. One of them is an algorithm for convex hull construction. This requires a somewhat different dual transformation, which maps the given set of points

$$P = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$$

into the set of halfplanes

$$D(P_i) = \{(x, y) \mid x_i \cdot x + y_i \cdot y \geq 1\}.$$

Optical realization of this transformation is essentially the same as the algorithm for points-to-dual-line mapping. Therefore, we omit its description. The resulting image is thus

$$\sum_{i=1}^N 1_{D(P_i)}(x, y).$$

Therefore, the dual polygon $D(\text{conv}(P))$ of the convex hull of the set P may be found by the formula

$$D(P) = \text{Threshold}_N^1\left(\sum_{i=1}^N 1_{D(P_i)}(x, y)\right),$$

if the origin of coordinate system is in the hull (otherwise, we can shift the image by the vector $-\frac{1}{3}(P_1 + P_2 + P_3)$ to be sure that the origin is in the hull). Next we can readily find the boundary of this polygon and using the Hough transform we can obtain the set of parameters

$$\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^M,$$

of the boundary segments of the convex hull. Using the above described technique, we can transform this set of parameters, which in fact is the set of points in coordinates (p, θ) , into the set of points

$$\left\{\left(\frac{\cos \theta_i}{p_i}, \frac{\sin \theta_i}{p_i}\right)\right\}_{i=1}^M,$$

which is the set of the vertices of the required convex hull. One can easily see that all these transformations require $O(1)$ optical operations. So, we obtain the following:

Theorem 4.3.1 *The convex hull of a planar set of points can be constructed optically in constant time (provided we have a filter capable of distinguishing between $O(N)$ levels of intensity).*

Figure 4.7: Images $P, P_{a_i \cdot b_i > 0}, P_{a_i \cdot b_i < 0}, P_{a_i = 0}$ and $P_{b_i = 0}$ respectively

Figure 4.8: Images $\{(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln \frac{b_i}{a_i})\}_{i=1}^{N_1}$, $\{(\frac{1}{a_i}, -\ln(-\frac{b_i}{a_i}))\}_{i=N_1+1}^{N_2}$, $\{(0, \frac{1}{b_i})\}_{i=N_2+1}^{N_3}$ and $\{(\frac{1}{a_i}, 0)\}_{i=N_3+1}^{N_4}$ respectively

Figure 4.9: Image $L_1(s, t)$

Figure 4.10: Image $L_2(s, t)$

Figure 4.11: Image $L_3(s, t)$

Figure 4.12: Image $L_4(s, t)$

Figure 4.13: Image $L_5(s, t)$

Figure 4.14: Image $L_6(s, t)$

Figure 4.15: Images obtained at step 4.

Figure 4.16: Dual lines of the given point set

Chapter 5

The Power of Duality and Minkowski Sums in Optical Computational Geometry

Geometric duality between points and straight lines in the plane is a powerful tool in standard computational geometry [CGL]. Minkowski sums are also a useful construct in standard computational geometry for several geometric problems, such as polygon placements and motion planning (see e.g. [K89, KLPS]).

In optical computational geometry, these operations are used in a completely different manner than in conventional computational geometry, as we have already seen in the previous chapters. Specifically, the combinatorial, discrete aspect of these operations is lost in the optical model, where data is represented directly in the form of a physical image, and no discrete data structures, such as arrays, trees, etc., are available. Nevertheless, as already done, and as we will show below, duality and Minkowski sums can be applied *en masse* to an optical frame, allowing us to perform the same operation simultaneously on all data objects in the frame, or even on all pairs of data objects, and resulting in a variety of rather subtle optical computational tricks that facilitate efficient implementations of more ‘advanced’ constructions in computational geometry than those already given.

Here is a list of problems that we study in this chapter and show how to solve each of them in $O(1)$ optical steps:

- Finding a separator line for a set of segments in the plane;
- Drawing all straight lines passing through each pair of points in a given set of points in the plane;
- Drawing all straight line segments connecting pairs of points between two given planar point sets;
- Erasing marked segments from a frame;

- Constructing the K -level of an arrangement of lines in the plane;
- Constructing a bisector of a finite set of points and ham-sandwich cuts in two dimensions;
- Reporting the K closest/farthest pairs of points in a given planar point set;
- Slope selection and reporting the K leftmost points in a planar point set;
- Drawing K shortest/longest segments connecting points in the plane;
- Extracting vertices of a polygon from its boundary;
- An improved optical convex hull algorithm;
- Multiple ray-shooting in a polygonal region;
- Constructing the visible portion of a polygon from an edge;
- Constructing Voronoi diagrams.
- Triangulation of a planar point set.

The last two algorithms require the polychromatic mode of Chapter 3 to run in $O(1)$ steps. All the other algorithms require $O(1)$ optical steps in the monochromatic mode.

5.1 Finding a Separator Line for a Set of Segments

A line L is called a *separator* for a set S of objects in the plane if L avoids all the objects and partitions S into two nonempty subsets (see [ERS]). In this section we consider the problem of constructing optically a separator line for a set of segments.

In a dual setting, the problem looks as follows. The given segments are dualized into double wedges, and a separator line is dualized into a point lying in the complement of the union of these double wedges, strictly between the upper and lower envelopes of the double wedges [ERS]. Hence, we can propose the following optical algorithm for finding the set of all possible separators:

Step 1. Dualize all points of the segments into their dual lines. As a result, the segments are dualized into the union of double wedges $\bigcup_{e \in S} DW(e)$.

The upper (lower) envelope of the double wedges is the collection of all points of the lines bounding the double wedges, which are visible from $y = +\infty$ ($y = -\infty$). Hence we can proceed as follows:

Step 2. Construct the upper and lower envelopes using the algorithm for hidden lines removal from section 2.1.3.

Step 3. Construct the following Minkowski sums:

$$above_upper_envelope = upper_envelope + ray_up;$$

$$below_lower_envelope = lower_envelope + ray_down,$$

where ray_up and ray_down are rays emanating from the origin along the y -axis upwards and downwards, respectively.

Step 4. Construct the set of dual points of all separators as follows:

$$P = \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \bigcup_{e \in S} DW(e) \setminus above_upper_envelope \setminus below_lower_envelope.$$

Step 5. If P is not empty (which can be determined by comparing intensities of light before and after passing through a SLM representing P), then choose a point from P and dualize it into a separator line. We can choose, for example, the lowest point among all leftmost points of P , as follows:

$$lowest_leftmost_point = P \setminus Threshold_1[(P \setminus Threshold_1(P + ray)) + ray_up],$$

where ray is the binary image storing the positive half of the x -axis.

Thus, we obtain

Theorem 5.1.1 *A separator line for a set of segments in the plane can be constructed optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.2 Drawing Straight Lines Between all Pairs of Given Points

Let $P = \{p_i = (x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given point set on an optical frame. We consider the problem of drawing, on an output frame, all possible straight lines passing through each pair of points in P . We can solve this problem as follows:

Step 1. Dualize the points $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ into the respective straight lines

$$\{(x, y) | x_i \cdot x + y_i \cdot y = 1\}_{i=1}^N.$$

Since, each dual line is the union of six images (see section 4.2, Fig. 4.14, 4.14, 4.15, and 4.16) each of which consists of parallel lines of unit brightness, the desired intersection points are those points of the union which have brightness 2, and we can extract them as follows:

Step 2. Filter all intersection points of these lines by thresholding the resulting image at intensity level 2.

Step 3. Dualize the resulting intersection points back into straight lines. Obviously, these lines are the desired lines which connect each pair of points in P .

We can extend this technique to the situation where we are given two planar point sets, $P = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and $Q = \{q_j\}_{j=1}^M$, and we want to draw on an output frame all the lines supporting the segments $\overline{p_i q_j}$, for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $j = 1, \dots, M$. This can be performed as follows:

Step 1. Dualize the points of P into an image L_P of N dual lines, as above. Transform L_P so that each point with non-zero brightness is assigned brightness 1.

Step 2. Similarly, dualize the points of Q into an image L_Q of M dual lines, and assign to them a uniform brightness of 1.

Step 3. Compute all intersection points of the previously constructed images, as in the preceding algorithm.

Step 4. Dualize the resulting intersection image to obtain an image consisting of all the desired connecting lines.

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.2.1 *Drawing on an optical frame all straight lines passing through each pair of points in a given planar set can be performed optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.3 Drawing All Segments Connecting a Pair of Point Sets

Let two planar point sets $A = \{a_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and $B = \{b_j\}_{j=1}^N$ be given (see Fig. 5.1). The problem that we consider next is to simultaneously draw on an optical frame all segments $\overline{a_i b_j}$, for $i, j = 1, \dots, N$.

Obviously,

$$\overline{a_i b_j} = a_i + \overline{b_j - a_i},$$

where $+$ and $-$ denote Minkowski sum and difference, respectively, and $\overline{b_j - a_i}$ denotes the segment connecting the origin to the point $b_j - a_i$.

Thus, to draw all segments $\overline{a_i b_j}$, we should first draw all segments $\overline{b_j - a_i}$. This can be done as follows:

Step 1. Compute the Minkowski difference $B - A$ (see Fig. 5.2).

Step 2. Draw all segments $\overline{b_j - a_i}$, for all i, j , using the algorithm described in section 2.2.2. Denote the resulting collection of segments by $\overline{B - A}$ (see Fig. 5.3).

Step 3. Compute the set $\overline{A - \overline{B}}$, in a symmetric manner.

We claim that if $A \cap B = \emptyset$, then the set $S = [A + \overline{B - A}] \cap [B + \overline{A - B}]$ contains all the desired segments $\{\overline{a_i b_j}\}_{i,j=1}^N$, and does not contain any other point except for isolated intersection points between translated copies of these segments. To see this, consider a segment $\overline{a_i b_j}$. It is clearly contained in S , because $\overline{a_i b_j} = a_i + \overline{b_j - a_i} = b_j + \overline{a_i - b_j}$. It is also possible that S contains a portion of a translated copy of this segment, but for this to

happen, there have to exist two other points $a_k \in A$, $b_\ell \in B$, such that $\overline{a_k b_\ell}$ has the same orientation as $\overline{a_i b_j}$. Then S contains the intersection segment $(a_k + \overline{(b_j - a_i)}) \cap (b_\ell + \overline{(a_i - b_j)})$, but this is always a subset of $\overline{a_k b_\ell}$. This establishes the claim.

The above argument holds as long as A and B are disjoint. If $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$, then $a_i = b_n$ for some i and n and S can contain spurious segments like the following

$$a_i + \overline{b_m - a_k} = b_n + \overline{a_j - b_l},$$

which connect no point of A to B (this can be seen for the special case where $A = B = \{p, q\}$, for any pair of points p, q , see Fig. 5.4).

Thus, to exclude spurious segments we should forbid the situation where segments in $A + \overline{B - A}$ are emanated in the same direction as in $B + \overline{A - B}$. We can achieve this by introducing the following notation

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{(B - A)}_+ &= \overline{B - A} \cap \{(x, y) | y > 0 \vee y = 0 \& x > 0\}; \\ \overline{(B - A)}_- &= \overline{B - A} \cap \{(x, y) | y < 0 \vee y = 0 \& x < 0\}; \\ \overline{(A - B)}_+ &= \overline{A - B} \cap \{(x, y) | y > 0 \vee y = 0 \& x > 0\}; \\ \overline{(A - B)}_- &= \overline{A - B} \cap \{(x, y) | y < 0 \vee y = 0 \& x < 0\}, \end{aligned}$$

we can see that $\{[A + \overline{(B - A)}_+] \cap [B + \overline{(A - B)}_-]\} \cup \{[A + \overline{(B - A)}_-] \cap [B + \overline{(A - B)}_+]\}$ contains all desired segments $\{\overline{A_i B_j}\}_{i,j=1}^N$ and does not contain any other segments (except for isolated intersection points (if any) between these segments), even if $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. This is because $\overline{(b_m - a_k)}_+$ cannot be equal to $\overline{(a_j - b_l)}_-$ and, hence, spurious segments cannot appear (see Fig. 5.5).

Thus, we can proceed as follows:

Step 4. Construct

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{(B - A)}_+ &= \overline{B - A} \cap \{(x, y) | y > 0 \vee y = 0 \& x > 0\}; \\ \overline{(B - A)}_- &= \overline{B - A} \cap \{(x, y) | y < 0 \vee y = 0 \& x < 0\}; \\ \overline{(A - B)}_+ &= \overline{A - B} \cap \{(x, y) | y > 0 \vee y = 0 \& x > 0\}; \\ \overline{(A - B)}_- &= \overline{A - B} \cap \{(x, y) | y < 0 \vee y = 0 \& x < 0\}, \end{aligned}$$

(see Fig. 5.6).

Step 5. Construct

$$\begin{aligned} S = \{[A + \overline{(B - A)}_+] \cap [B + \overline{(A - B)}_-]\} \cup \{[A + \overline{(B - A)}_-] \cap [B + \overline{(A - B)}_+]\} = \\ \{\overline{A_i B_j}\}_{i,j=1}^N \cup \text{isolated_intersection_points}, \end{aligned}$$

(see Fig. 5.7–5.9).

To remove the annoying isolated intersection points, we need to introduce the notion of brightness of the Minkowski sum:

Definition 5.3.1 Let $U + V$ be the Minkowski sum of two planar sets U and V . We define the brightness of the sum at a point p as

$$\text{brightness}(U + V, p) = \#\{q \mid q \in U; p \in V + q\}.$$

(We note that, when computing the Minkowski sum optically, the brightness as just defined corresponds to actual optical brightness, as follows from the algorithm given in section 2.1.1).

Obviously, if U or V are finite point sets, then $U + V$ has finite brightness at each point; if U and V are non-colinear segments, then $U + V$ also has finite brightness everywhere; but the sum of two colinear segments has infinite brightness at each point of the sum, except for its endpoints.

These properties allow us to get rid of the isolated intersection points in S (see Fig. 5.10) as follows:

Step 6. Construct $U = \overline{A - B} \cup \overline{B - A}$.

Step 7. Construct

$$U_+ = U \cap \{(x, y) \mid x^2 + y^2 < \epsilon^2; \quad (y > 0 \vee y = 0 \ \& \ x > 0)\};$$

$$U_- = U \cap \{(x, y) \mid x^2 + y^2 < \epsilon^2; \quad (y < 0 \vee y = 0 \ \& \ x < 0)\},$$

where 2ϵ is a lower bound on the minimum distance between any pair of points belonging to the union $A \cup B$. (Intersections of this kind use ‘constant’ frames, such as the characteristic function of $\{(x, y) \mid x^2 + y^2 < \epsilon^2; \quad y > 0 \vee y = 0 \ \& \ x > 0\}$, that are precomputed and stored in the optical memory of the computer. If ϵ is not given in advance and has to be computed, as will be described below, then the disc $x^2 + y^2 < \epsilon^2$ can be easily computed by the techniques described in section 2.3.1.)

Obviously, $U_+ = \{\lambda_{ij}(\overline{b_j - a_i})\}_{i,j=1}^N$ and $U_- = \{-\lambda_{ij}(\overline{b_j - a_i})\}_{i,j=1}^N$, where

$$\lambda_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{\epsilon}{\rho(a_i, b_j)}, & \text{if } (b_j)_y > (a_i)_y \\ & \vee (b_j)_y = (a_i)_y \ \& \ (b_j)_x > (a_i)_x; \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\rho(a_i, b_j)}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

and $\rho(p, q)$ denotes the distance between p and q .

Step 8. Construct $U_+ + S$ (see Fig. 5.11), which is equal to

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup \{ \overline{a_i b_j} + \lambda_{ij}(\overline{b_j - a_i}) \mid 1 \leq i, j \leq N \} \cup \\ & \bigcup \{ \overline{a_i b_j} + \lambda_{k\ell}(\overline{b_\ell - a_k}) \mid 1 \leq i, j, k, \ell \leq N; \overline{a_i b_j} \text{ not parallel to } \overline{a_k b_\ell} \} \cup \\ & \bigcup [U_+ + (\text{isolated_intersection_points})]. \end{aligned}$$

As is easily seen, only the first term on the right hand side contains points with infinite brightness. Thus:

Step 9. Filter out, by thresholding $U_+ + S$ at a sufficiently large brightness, the first set

$$V_1 = \bigcup_{i,j=1}^N [\overline{a_i b_j} + \lambda_{ij}(\overline{b_j - a_i})],$$

(see Fig. 5.12).

Step 10. In a symmetric manner, using U_- instead of U_+ , construct the set

$$V_2 = \bigcup_{i,j=1}^N [\overline{a_i b_j} - \lambda_{ij}(\overline{b_j - a_i})],$$

(see Fig. 5.13).

Step 11. The desired collection of segments, $\bigcup_{i,j=1}^N \overline{a_i b_j}$ is finally obtained as the intersection $V_1 \cap V_2$ (see Fig. 5.14). The above choice of ϵ guarantees correctness of this step, as is easily checked.

The proposed algorithm requires computation of a lower bound on the minimum distance between points in a given planar set. Such a bound can be computed as follows:

Step 1. Project the given point set P onto the x -axis, by performing the semi-conformal coordinate transformation $(x, y) \rightarrow (x, 0)$. Let P_x denote the resulting image.

Step 2. Similarly, compute the projection P_y of P onto the y -axis.

Step 3. Compute the Minkowski difference $P_x - P_x$, and, by an appropriate thresholding, assign to each point there the same brightness 1. Denote the resulting set by ΔP_x .

Step 4. Compute in a symmetric manner the set ΔP_y from the projection P_y .

Step 5. Construct

$$V = (\Delta P_x \cap ray) + ray,$$

where $ray = \{(x, y) \mid x \geq 0; y = 0\}$.

If ΔP_x consists of the points $(0, \delta_1, \delta_2, \dots)$ in this order, then the effect of the last operation is to partition the positive x -axis into intervals, delimited by these points, so that the brightness of the i -th interval from the left (closed on the left and open on the right side) is equal to i . Hence:

Step 6. Construct $V \cap \Delta P_x$ and filter out from it the (unique) point at brightness 2.

This point is equal to

$$\epsilon_x = \min_{\substack{a, b \in P \\ a \neq b}} |a_x - b_x|.$$

Step 7. Compute, in a fully symmetric manner,

$$\epsilon_y = \min_{\substack{a, b \in P \\ a \neq b}} |a_y - b_y|.$$

Step 8. Compute $\epsilon = \min\{\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y\}$; this is clearly a lower bound on the smallest distance between the given points.

This completes the description of the algorithm, leading to the following summary result:

Theorem 5.3.2 *One can draw on an optical frame all segments connecting between points in two given planar sets, using a constant number of optical operations by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

Remark: The second part of the above algorithm deals exclusively with the problem of getting rid of the isolated intersection points. It is not difficult to extend the technique so that, given a frame consisting of some segments and some isolated points, produces an output frame in which only the segments remain and the isolated points are erased or vice versa.

5.4 Erasing Segments from a Frame

Let $S = \{s_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given collection of segments drawn on an optical frame. We want to erase some of these segments, and assume that each segment to be erased is marked by a point lying on it. Let P denote the set of marking points. These points are assumed either to be given on a separate optical frame, or to lie in the same frame as S but to have larger brightness than that of the remaining points on the segments of S (so that one can distinguish these points by thresholding). Let S_- denote the subset of segments to be erased, and let S_+ denote the subset of segments to be left on the frame.

Let us first suppose that there are no two distinct segments in S whose supporting lines pass through the same marking point. Then the required erasing is easily performed as follows:

Step 1. Dualize the points in P into a collection L_P of lines, and the (lines supporting the) segments in S into a collection P_S of points.

Step 2. Construct the set of points dual to those segments which should not be removed:

$$P_{S_+} = P_S \setminus L_P.$$

Step 3. Dualize P_{S_+} back into a collection L_+ supporting those segments to be left on the frame.

Step 4. Construct

$$S \cap L_+ = (S_+ \cup S_-) \cap L_+ = S_+ \cup [\{\text{isolated_points_of_}S_-\} \cap L_+].$$

Step 5. Get rid of the isolated intersection points, in an analogous manner to that in the previous section, to obtain S_+ . (See the remark at the end of the previous section.)

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.4.1 *Removing some of the segments drawn on a frame can be performed optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode, provided the segments to be removed are not colinear.*

5.5 Constructing the k -level of an Arrangement of Lines in the Plane

Let $A(L)$ be an arrangement of a set L of N lines in the plane. The k -level of $A(L)$, for $1 \leq k \leq N$, is defined as the set of points p with

$$a(p) \leq k - 1 \text{ and } b(p) \leq N - k,$$

where $a(p)$, $b(p)$ are the number of lines l in L such that p is in the (open) halfplane l^+ , and l^- , respectively.

Our approach to constructing the k -level of an arrangement of lines optically is based on the following definition and lemma:

Definition 5.5.1 Let $\bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i$ be the union of N planar sets. We define the brightness of the union at point p as the number of sets A_i containing p :

$$\text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N A_i) = \#\{i | p \in A_i\}.$$

(We note that, when computing union of sets optically, by adding up their characteristic functions, the brightness as just defined corresponds to actual optical brightness.)

Lemma 5.5.2 The k -level of an arrangement of a set $L = \{l_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of N lines coincides with the lower envelope of that portion of $\bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c$ which has brightness k , except at intersection points of the lines.

Proof. Indeed, let $\text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c) = k$. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c) &= \#\{i | p \in (l_i^-)^c\} = \\ &= \#\{i | p \in l_i^+ \vee p \in l_i\} = \#\{i | p \in l_i^+\} + \#\{i | p \in l_i\} = a(p) + \#\{i | p \in l_i\} = k. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$a(p) = k - \#\{i | p \in l_i\}.$$

However, p lies on at least one line l_i because p belongs to the above lower envelope. Hence $\#\{i | p \in l_i\} \geq 1$ and $a(p) \leq k - 1$.

On the other hand,

$$b(p) = \#\{i | p \in l_i^-\} = N - \#\{i | p \in (l_i^-)^c\} = N - \text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c) = N - k.$$

Since we proved that both $a(p) \leq k - 1$ and $b(p) = N - k$, p belongs to the k -level of $A(L)$.

Let us now prove that if, conversely, p belongs to the k -level of $A(L)$ and is not an intersection point of the lines, then $\text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c) = k$.

Indeed, since p is not an intersection point, then $a(p) + b(p) = N - 1$ and, hence, $a(p) = k - 1$, $b(p) = N - k$. Thus,

$$\text{brightness}(p, \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c) = a(p) + \#\{i | p \in l_i\} = a(p) + 1 = k.$$

Similarly, we can see that no point vertically below p can have brightness k , thus p lies on the desired lower envelope. □

Based on this lemma, we can propose the following algorithm for constructing the k -level of an arrangements of lines $L = \{l_i\}_{i=1}^N$ in the plane:

Step 1. Compute

$$L + \text{ray_down} = \bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c,$$

where ray_down is the binary image storing the negative half of the y -axis.

Step 2. Compute

$$\text{Belt}_k = \text{Threshold}_k\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^N (l_i^-)^c\right)$$

and construct, thereby, all points in the plane which have k -level except at intersection points of the lines $L = \{l_i\}_{i=1}^N$.

Step 3. Construct that portion of Belt_k which is visible from the point at $y = -\infty$. As a result, we obtain the desired k -level except at those points which are intersection points of the lines constituting the arrangement.

To augment the image obtained by the finite number of missing points and complete thereby the construction of the k -level of an arrangement, we can proceed as follows:

Step 4. Compute a lower bound 2ϵ on the minimum distance between any pair of the intersection points of the lines. (We can do it with the help of the algorithm from section 5.3.)

Step 5. Construct all possible segments S_ϵ of length ϵ emanating from the origin, which are parallel to the segments of the k -level of the arrangement, as just constructed (the details of performing this are described below).

Step 6. Construct the Minkowski sum of S_ϵ with the constructed portion of the k -level, and extract that portion of the sum which has infinite brightness.

It is easily seen that the image obtained contains those and only those intersection points of the lines of L which belong to the k -level. Hence, we can proceed as follows:

Step 7. Construct the intersection of the image obtained at step 7 with the entire set of intersection points of the lines of L . As a result, we obtain the missing points of the desired k -level.

Step 8. Complete the construction by taking the union of those portions of it obtained at steps 4 and 8 respectively.

The proposed algorithm requires the construction of the set S_ϵ , which can be performed as follows:

Step 1. Hough-dualize all segments of the constructed portion of the k -level into their Hough points $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ (see section 4.1).

Step 2. Perform the coordinate transformation

$$\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N \longrightarrow \{(0, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N.$$

Step 3. Hough-dualize the points $\{(0, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ back to the straight lines which are parallel to the segments of the k -level and pass through the origin.

Step 4. Construct S_ϵ by intersecting the lines obtained with the disc of radius ϵ around the origin.

Hence, we obtain

Theorem 5.5.3 *The k -level of an arrangement of lines in the plane, as well as the region between the k -level and $(k + 1)$ -level, can be constructed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.6 Constructing a Bisector of a Finite Set of Points and Ham-Sandwich Cuts in Two Dimensions

A line L is called a *bisector* of a finite set P of points in \mathbb{R}^2 if each open half-plane defined by L contains at most half of the points in P .

If we pass from the original plane to the dual plane, the set P becomes a set $D(P)$ of dual lines and a bisector L turns into a point $D(L)$ lying between the $\lfloor \frac{N}{2} \rfloor$ -level and the $\lceil \frac{N}{2} \rceil$ -level of the arrangement $A(D(P))$. Hence, we can propose the following algorithm for constructing a bisector:

Step 1. Dualize the given point set P into set of dual half-planes $D^+(P)$.

Step 2. Threshold $D^+(P)$ to select all points at the $\lfloor \frac{N}{2} \rfloor$ -level of intensity. As a result, we obtain dual points of all possible bisectors.

Step 3. Choose a point from the set obtained and dualize it into a bisector (see section 5.1 for the procedure of choosing a point from the set.)

A common bisector of two finite point sets (i.e. a Ham-sandwich cut of the sets) is constructed in a similar manner. First, we construct separately dual points of all possible bisectors of the first set and of the second set. Then we construct the intersection of these two sets of dual points and choose a point from the intersection. The point chosen is the dual point of a common bisector. Thus we obtain

Theorem 5.6.1 *A bisector of a finite point set in the plane, as well as a ham-sandwich cut of two finite point sets, can be constructed optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.7 Extracting Vertices of a Polygonal Image

Recall that the boundary of an arbitrary image can be easily extracted by spatial differentiation of the image (see section 1.1.4). Hence, our problem is converted into the problem of extracting vertices of a polygon A from its boundary $\partial A = \bigcup_{i=1}^N S_i$, consisting of edges S_i .

To perform it we can proceed as follows:

Step 1. Dualize the edges $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N$ into points and then dualize back these points into the union of straight lines $L = \bigcup_{i=1}^N l_i$ supporting these edges (see Fig. 5.15).

Step 2. Extract the intersection points $Q = \{Q_i\}_{i=1}^M$ of the lines by thresholding the image obtained at level 2. Obviously, Q contains all vertices of A and intersection points of its boundary with lines in L and between pairs of lines in L . The latter two kinds of points can be considered as redundant vertices. To get rid of them we can proceed as follows:

Step 3. Compute $P = \partial A \cap Q$. Obviously, P contains all vertices of A and intersection points of its boundary with lines in L .

Step 4. Choose an $\epsilon > 0$ such that the disc of radius ϵ centered at any point $p \in P$ does not contain other points of P and does not intersect edges of the polygon except for the edge(s) that contain p (the details of performing this step are described below).

Step 5. Compute the following segments of boundary edges:

$$S = \partial A \cap (P + O_\epsilon),$$

where O_ϵ is the disc of radius ϵ centered at the origin of coordinates (see Fig. 5.16).

It is easily seen that each segment $s \in S$ has length ϵ or 2ϵ , depending on whether or not one of its endpoints is a vertex of A .

Step 6. Construct all radial segments R of O_ϵ which are parallel to the edges of the polygon, as in the algorithm of section 5.5.

Step 7. Compute

$$\text{Threshold}_\infty(S + R).$$

It is easily seen that the image obtained consists of segments lying completely in the boundary of the polygon unless they pass through its vertices (see Fig 5.17). Hence,

$$\text{Threshold}_\infty(S + R) \setminus \partial A$$

is a set of exterior open segments, each of which has a vertex of A as an endpoint and lies on an extension of an incident edges. We refer to these segments as “pointers” at the vertices, and construct them by:

Step 8.

$$\text{pointers_at_vertices} = \text{Threshold}_\infty(S + R) \setminus \partial A,$$

(see Fig. 5.18).

Step 9. Elongate the pointers by computing

$$\text{lengthened_pointers} = \text{Threshold}_\infty(\text{pointers_at_vertices} + R),$$

(see Fig. 5.19).

Obviously, due to the above choice of ϵ , *lengthened_pointers* contain all vertices of A and do not contain redundant vertices. Hence, we can complete the algorithm as follows:

Step 10. Compute

$$\text{Vertices} = P \cap \text{lengthened_pointers}.$$

Computing the required ϵ at Step 4 can be performed as follows:

Step 1. Rotate the set L of lines obtained in Step 1 of the previous algorithm by the angle $\frac{\pi}{2}$. This can be done using the following semi-conformal coordinate transformation:

$$\begin{cases} u = y \\ v = -x. \end{cases}$$

As a result we obtain a set L_1 of lines, each of which is perpendicular to a corresponding line of L .

Step 2. Hough-dualize the lines of L_1 into points (p_i, θ_i) , then transform these points into the corresponding points $(0, \theta_i)$, and finally Hough-dualize the new points back to set L_2 of lines which pass through the origin of the coordinates. Obviously, each line of L is perpendicular to at least one line of L_2 and vice versa.

Step 3. Compute the Minkowski sum $L_2 + P$. As a result we obtain the set of supporting lines of all the perpendiculars from the points of P to the edges $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of the polygon.

Step 4. Compute the set Q of all the intersection points between the edges of A and the perpendiculars to these edges from the points of P , constructed at the previous step.

Step 5. Compute a lower bound 2ϵ on the minimum distance between any pair of the points in $P \cup Q$. Obviously, such ϵ satisfies the requirements of Step 4 of the previous algorithm.

Hence, we obtain

Theorem 5.7.1 *The vertices of a polygonal image can be extracted optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.8 Reporting the K Closest (or Farthest) Distances among Points in the Plane

Let $P = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given planar point set. We next consider the problem of reporting the K closest (or farthest) distances between these points. This is done as follows:

Step 1. Construct the Minkowski difference $P - P = \{p_i - p_j\}_{i,j=1}^N$.

Step 2. Remove the origin from the image $P - P$, to obtain a new image ΔP .

Step 3. Perform the following chain of semi-conformal coordinate transformations on ΔP :

$$(u, v) \longrightarrow (u^2 + v^2, 2uv) \longrightarrow \\ (u^2 + v^2, 0) \longrightarrow (\sqrt{u^2 + v^2}, 0),$$

thereby obtaining the set $D = \{(d_{ij}, 0)\}_{i,j=1}^N$, where d_{ij} denotes the distance between p_i and p_j .

Step 4. Compute the Minkowski sum

$$S = D + ray,$$

where ray is the binary image storing the positive half of the x -axis.

One can easily verify that $brightness(S, (d_{ij}, 0)) = rank(d_{ij})$, where $rank(d_{ij})$ denotes the rank of d_{ij} in the ordered sequence of distances (each counted with the appropriate multiplicity) among the points of P .

Thus, if we intersect S with D and then filter the resulting image at level K , we obtain the desired K closest distances (as points on the x -axis).

The algorithm for reporting the K farthest pairs of points is the same except for Step 4 where instead of computing $S = D + ray$ we should compute $S = D - ray$. Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.8.1 *Reporting the K closest/farthest pairs of points in a given set can be performed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

We can stop here if we only need to report the K closest distances themselves. If we also need, say to draw the segments between the corresponding pairs of points of P , this can also be performed optically in constant time. The details of this procedure are given in the following section.

5.9 Drawing K Shortest (or Longest) Segments Connecting Points in the Plane

Let $P = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given planar point set. We next consider the problem of drawing K shortest/longest segments connecting these points. This can be done as follows:

Step 1. Draw all segments $\overline{p_i p_j}$ in parallel for each i, j .

Step 2. Perform the Hough transform of the image obtained. Obviously, under this transformation each segment $\overline{p_i p_j}$ converts into the point (p_{ij}, θ_{ij}) having brightness proportional to its length. Using theta-modulation described in the continuous model of computation (see refelem), we can separate the K brightest points as follows:

Step 3. Perform theta-modulation of the point image obtained. As a result, it converts into another point image:

$$\{(\pm \cos U_{ij}, \pm \sin U_{ij})\}_{i,j=1;i \neq j}^N,$$

where U_{ij} is the brightness of the point (p_{ij}, θ_{ij}) . We assume that $U_{ij} \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$. This condition can be satisfied by a proper scaling of the brightness of the image, if necessary.

Step 4. Perform the following coordinate transformation of the image obtained:

$$\{(\pm \cos U_{ij}, \pm \sin U_{ij})\}_{i,j} \longrightarrow \{(0, \sin U_{ij})\}_{i,j}.$$

In what follows we denote $\sin U_{ij}$ by Y_{ij} .

Step 5. Construct

$$S = \{(0, Y_{ij})\}_{i,j} + ray_down,$$

where

$$ray_down = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = 0; y \leq 0; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Obviously, the K highest points of $\{(0, Y_{ij})\}$ have brightness at most K in the image constructed and correspond to the K largest segments connecting points of P . Hence, we should proceed as follows:

Step 6. Extract that part of S which has brightness at most K . Denote the part by $\overline{Slice}_K(S)$.

Step 7. Extract the K highest points $\{(0, Y_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K$ from the set $\{(0, Y_{ij})\}_{i,j=1;i \neq j}^N$ by:

$$\{(0, Y_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K = \overline{Slice}_K(S) \cap \{(0, Y_{ij})\}_{i,j=1;i \neq j}^N.$$

Step 8. Construct

$$R = \{(0, Y_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K + ray,$$

where ray is the binary image storing the positive half of the x -axis.

Step 9. Construct

$$\{(\cos U_{i_m j_m}, \sin U_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K = R \cap \{(x, y) | x^2 + y^2 = 1; x \geq 0\}.$$

Step 10. Perform demodulation of the image constructed. As a result we obtain points $\{(p_{i_m j_m}, \theta_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K$ having intensities $\{\rho(p_{i_m}, p_{j_m})\}_{m=1}^K$, respectively.

Step 11. Dualize the point set $\{(p_{i_m j_m}, \theta_{i_m j_m})\}_{m=1}^K$ into the supporting lines of the segments $\{\overline{p_{i_m} p_{j_m}}\}_{m=1}^K$. Finally, intersect these supporting lines with the segments constructed at Step 1, to obtain the desired K longest segments.

The algorithm for drawing K shortest segments is analogous. Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.9.1 *Drawing the K shortest/longest segments connecting points of a planar point set can be performed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.10 An Algorithm for Slope Selection

Let an integer k and a set of N points $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ in the plane be given. The slope selection problem is to select that pair of points that determines the line with the k^{th} smallest or largest slope. In the dual plane this problem is converted into the problem of reporting the k^{th} leftmost vertex of the arrangement of the lines dual to the given point. This in turn is easily converted, by projection, into the problem of determining the k^{th} leftmost point among points on X -axis. The latter problem has been solved in section 5.8.

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.10.1 *The slope selection problem can be solved optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

5.11 An Improved Optical Convex Hull Algorithm

The problem of designing efficient optical algorithms for computing convex hulls in the plane has been addressed in the previous sections. The optical convex hull algorithm described in section 2.2.4 required $O(N)$ optical steps and a thresholding filter capable of distinguishing between $O(1)$ levels of brightness. Attempts to speed up the construction led to another algorithm (see section 4.3) requiring $O(1)$ steps, but with a filter capable of distinguishing between up to $O(N)$ levels of brightness.

In this section we present an improved optical convex hull algorithm that requires only $O(1)$ optical steps and a filter capable of distinguishing between only $O(1)$ levels of brightness.

The algorithm is rather simple. Let $P = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given planar point set. To compute its convex hull, we proceed as follows.

Step 1. Draw all segments $\{\overline{p_i p_j}\}_{i,j=1}^N$.

Step 2. Connect one fixed point of P , say p_1 , with all points on the constructed segments.

This obviously yields the desired convex hull.

Theorem 5.11.1 *Constructing the convex hull of a planar point set can be performed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode and which is capable of distinguishing between only $O(1)$ levels of brightness.*

5.12 Multiple Ray-Shooting in a Polygon

We next consider the following problem. Let P be a filled polygonal region in the plane, which we assume to be represented on an optical frame by its characteristic function. We are also given a collection $R = \{\rho_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of rays, whose starting points all lie on a fixed edge e of ∂P . We assume, with no real loss of generality, that e lies on the x -axis, that P is fully contained in the upper half-plane $y \geq 0$, and that the rays in R are all upward-directed. The problem is to compute the *initial segment* of each $\rho \in R$ in P , namely the connected

component of $\rho \cap P$ that contains the origin of ρ (this also yields implicitly the first point of intersection of each ray ρ with the boundary of P).

We can solve the problem as follows (see Figs. 5.20–5.23 for an illustration of some of the steps of the algorithm):

Step 1. Draw all portions of rays of R that lie outside of P :

$$S = \bigcup R \setminus P.$$

Step 2. Translate all the rays in R to the origin of the coordinate system, as follows:

Substep 2.1 Hough dualize R into a point set $\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ (where point (p, θ) represents the line $x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta = p$;

Substep 2.2 Perform the semi-conformal coordinate transformation:

$$\{(p_i, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N \longrightarrow \{(0, \theta_i)\}_{i=1}^N.$$

Substep 2.3 Dualize the resulting point set back into a collection of straight lines (all passing through the origin of the coordinate system).

Substep 2.4 Extract those parts of the lines which are above the x -axis. As a result we obtain a new set R_1 of rays each parallel to a corresponding ray in R but emanating from the origin.

Step 3. Construct

$$R_2 = S + \bigcup R_1.$$

It is easily checked that those portions of the rays of R that should be removed to obtain the initial segments, are exactly those points in R_2 that have infinite brightness. Thus:

Step 4. Extract the collection R_3 of subrays of rays in R_2 which have infinite brightness.

Step 5. The desired collection of initial segments of the rays of R is thus simply $\bigcup R \setminus R_3$.

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.12.1 *Given a collection of rays as above, the initial segment of each ray, between its first entry point into a polygonal region and its first exit point from the polygon, can be constructed optically in constant time by a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode.*

Remark: Note that we do not require P to be a simple polygon; the technique holds for an arbitrary, possibly multiply-connected, polygonal region.

5.13 Weak Visibility of a Polygon From an Edge

Let P be a polygonal region given by two optical frames, the first of which contains the vertices of the polygon, $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$, and the second frame contains its boundary edges $\{\overline{p_i p_{i+1}}\}_{i=1}^N$. A boundary point t is said to be *weakly visible* from the edge $e = \overline{p_1 p_2}$ if it is visible from at least one point of the edge. As is known [GHLST], the weakly visible points constitute a subpolygon of P , each of whose vertices is either:

- 1) a vertex of P visible from e ; or
- 2) a shadow cast by a ray emanating from some point on e and passing through two vertices p_i and p_j .

As in the preceding section, we assume, with no loss of generality, that the polygon P is fully contained in a half-plane H bounded by the line supporting e .

Hence, the vertices of the weakly visible subpolygon can be obtained by performing multiple ray shooting for the set of those rays supporting the segments $\{\overline{p_i p_j}\}$ and intersecting e ; more precisely, each such ray starts at the point of intersection of the corresponding supporting line with e and emanates towards the halfplane H . Of course, this multiple ray shooting may produce spurious vertices, because we only want to consider those rays for which the two defining vertices p_i, p_j are visible from e . The algorithm will deal with this issue.

Step 1. Draw the collection S of all segments $\{\overline{p_i p_j}\}_{i,j=1,i \neq j}^N$.

Step 2. Construct the collection L of supporting lines of the segments in S .

Step 3. Remove from L those lines which do not intersect e , as follows:

Substep 3.1. Dualize the lines in L into a collection P_L of points.

Substep 3.2. Dualize e into an appropriate double wedge DW_e as follows:

$$DW_e = (D(p_1)^{pos} \cap D(p_2)^{neg}) \cup (D(p_1)^{neg} \cap D(p_2)^{pos}),$$

where $D(T)^{pos}$ denotes that dual halfplane of T which contains the origin of the coordinates ($D(T)^{neg}$ is defined analogously).

Substep 3.3. Let L_1 be the subset of lines in L which intersect e . The set P_{L_1} of points dual to those lines is simply $P_{L_1} = P_L \cap DW_e$.

Substep 3.4. Dualize P_{L_1} back into L_1 .

Step 4. Construct the collection IS of all initial segments within P of the rays contained in the lines of L_1 (as in the preceding section).

Step 5. Construct $IS \cap \partial P$. As a result we obtain the vertices of the weakly visible portion of P ; as noted above, some of these vertices may be redundant, but each of the resulting points does belong to the boundary of the visible portion, as is easily checked.

The subsequent reconstructing the entire weakly visible subpolygon from its vertices can be performed using the algorithm of section 3.1.

Thus, we obtain:

Theorem 5.13.1 *The vertices of a polygon weakly visible from an edge can be constructed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode. Entire portion of a polygon visible from an edge can be constructed optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the polychromatic mode.*

Remark: Note again that we do not require P to be a simple polygon; the technique holds for an arbitrary, possibly multiply-connected, polygonal region.

5.14 Constructing Voronoi Diagrams

Let $P = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^N$ be a given planar point set. The Voronoi diagram of P consists of Voronoi cells, one for each $p_i \in P$, defined as follows:

$$V(p_i) = \bigcap_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^N H_{ij}^+,$$

where H_{ij}^+ is the halfplane containing p_i whose boundary is the perpendicular bisector of $\overline{p_i p_j}$, i.e. the line passing through the point $\frac{1}{2}(p_i + p_j)$ and perpendicular to $\overline{p_i p_j}$.

As is easily seen, if the origin of the coordinate system is located at p_i , the polar coordinates of points in H_{ij}^+ satisfy:

$$\left(\frac{r}{r_{ij}} \leq \frac{1}{\cos(\theta - \theta_{ij})}\right) \& (|\theta - \theta_{ij}| \leq \frac{\pi}{2}) \vee \left(\frac{\pi}{2} < |\theta - \theta_{ij}| \leq \pi\right),$$

where (r_{ij}, θ_{ij}) are the polar coordinates of $\frac{1}{2}(p_i + p_j)$. The first inequality is equivalent to

$$\ln r - \ln r_{ij} \leq -\ln \cos(\theta - \theta_{ij}),$$

which suggests the following algorithm for constructing the Voronoi cell $V(p_i)$:

Step 1. Move the origin of the coordinate system to p_i .

Step 2. Construct $\frac{1}{2}(p_i + P)$. This is the set of all midpoints $\{(x_{ij}, y_{ij})\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^N$ of the segments $\{\overline{p_i p_j}\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^N$.

Step 3. Perform the log-polar mapping:

$$\{(x_{ij}, y_{ij})\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^N \longrightarrow \{(\ln r_{ij}, \theta_{ij})\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^N.$$

Step 4. Convolve the constructed point set with the following binary mask:

$$\text{domain}(u, v) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (|v| \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \& u \leq -\ln \cos v) \\ & \vee (\frac{\pi}{2} < |v| \leq \pi); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This produces the log-polar representation of $\bigcup_{j=1; j \neq i}^N H_{ij}^+$.

Step 5. Extract the portion of the above image which has brightness N , to obtain the log-polar representation of $\bigcap_{j=1; j \neq i}^N H_{ij}^+$.

Step 6. Return to cartesian coordinates, thus obtaining the desired Voronoi cell of p_i .

If we apply this procedure to each point $p_i \in P$, we obtain the collection of all Voronoi cells, and thus the Voronoi diagram of P . Unfortunately, this approach requires $O(N)$ optical operations in the monochromatic mode, but it can be easily executed in a constant number of steps in the polychromatic mode. We leave it as an open problem to design an optical algorithm that can construct the entire diagram in only a constant number of monochromatic operations.

Theorem 5.14.1 *A single Voronoi cell in the Voronoi diagram of a planar point set can be constructed optically in constant time by a single processor which works in the monochromatic mode. Consequently, the full Voronoi diagram can be constructed optically in constant time using N processors which work in the monochromatic mode, or a single processor which works in the polychromatic mode.*

5.15 Triangulations

The dual structure of the Voronoi diagram of a planar point set P is the Delaunay diagram of P . If one assumes that no four points of P are co-circular, this is a triangulation of (the convex hull of) P .

The following simple optical algorithm constructs all ‘half-edges’ of the Delaunay triangulation that connect a fixed point $p_i \in P$ to the midpoints of all segments between p_i and its Voronoi neighbors. By repeating this procedure for all points of P , we obtain the (complete edges of the) desired triangulation.

Step 1. Compute the Voronoi cell $V(p_i)$, as in the preceding section.

Step 2. Move the origin of the coordinate system to p_i .

Step 3. Dualize the lines $a_{ij}x + b_{ij}y = 1$ supporting the edges of the cell $V(p_i)$ into the set of points $M = \{(a_{ij}, b_{ij})\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^{N_i}$, where N_i is the number of edges in $V(p_i)$.

Step 4. Perform the semi-conformal coordinate transformation:

$$\begin{cases} u = \frac{x}{x^2+y^2}, \\ v = \frac{y}{x^2+y^2}. \end{cases}$$

As a result M is transformed into the set of points

$$M_1 = \left\{ \left(\frac{a_{ij}}{a_{ij}^2 + b_{ij}^2}, \frac{b_{ij}}{a_{ij}^2 + b_{ij}^2} \right) \right\}_{j=1; j \neq i}^{N_i}.$$

Step 5. Connect the origin with each point of M_1 .

Step 6. Translate the resulting image by p_i .

The correctness of this procedure is easily verified, leading to:

Theorem 5.15.1 *One can triangulate a planar point set in $O(N)$ optical operations, using an optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode, or in $O(1)$ operations by a processor which works in the polychromatic mode.*

Again, we leave it as an open problem whether such a triangulation can be constructed in $O(1)$ optical steps in the monochromatic mode.

Figure 5.1: $A \cup B$

Figure 5.2: $B - A$

Figure 5.3: Images $\overline{A - B}$ (left) and $\overline{B - A}$ (right)

Figure 5.4: Spurious segments arising when $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$.

Figure 5.5: Handling the spurious segments when $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$ with the help of the (+, -)-notation

Figure 5.6: Images $\overline{(A - B)}_+$, $\overline{(B - A)}_+$, $\overline{(A - B)}_-$, and $\overline{(B - A)}_-$, respectively

Figure 5.7: Images $A + \overline{(B - A)}_+$, $B + \overline{(A - B)}_-$, and their intersection, respectively

Figure 5.8: Images $A + \overline{(B - A)}_-$, $B + \overline{(A - B)}_+$, and their intersection, respectively

Figure 5.9: The image S obtained by union of images c) from the two previous figures. Fortunately, it contains the desired segments only and does not contain isolated intersection points that is not always the case

Figure 5.10: The image S containing both the desired segments and additional isolated intersection points

Figure 5.11: Amplification of the brightness of the segments with the help of the Minkowski sum

Figure 5.12: The image V_1 obtained by filtering the previous image

Figure 5.13: The image V_2

Figure 5.14: The desired segments obtained by intersection of the two previous images

Figure 5.15: A polygon, extensions of its edges and the intersection points of these extensions

Figure 5.16: Real and spurious vertices of the polygon, and the segments $S = \partial A \cap (P + O_\epsilon)$

Figure 5.17: The image $\text{Threshold}_\infty(S + R)$

Figure 5.18: Vertices and pointers at them

Figure 5.19: Vertices and lengthened pointers at them

Figure 5.20: Polygon and multiple rays

Figure 5.21: Segments of rays lying inside the polygon

Figure 5.22: Segments of rays lying outside the polygon

Figure 5.23: Amplification of the brightness of the undesired parts of rays with the help of the Minkowski sum

Chapter 6

Optical Filling Algorithm

So far we dealt with a continuous model of optical computations. However, not all problems are easy to solve in this model in constant time. One such problem is filling the interior of a plane figure. Trying to tackle it in the continuous model, we proposed in section 2.1.2 a filling algorithm which fills the interior up to a set of measure zero. Here we present an algorithm which performs the filling exactly. This algorithm is based on the discrete model of optical computation, as presented in section 1.1.3.

6.1 Optical Symbolic Substitution

The discrete model has the advantage over the continuous model that it provides a powerful technique for recognizing all occurrences of any combination of pixels in a discrete image and the substitution of each specific combination by another combination (in what follows combinations are called patterns). This technique is called symbolic substitution (SS) [H].

Recognition of all occurrences of a pattern and their substitution by another pattern is performed simultaneously. Such substitutions are denoted as follows:

$$P_1 \longrightarrow P_2,$$

where P_1 and P_2 denote the patterns to be recognized and to be substituted, respectively. The above relationship is called a rule of symbolic substitution. To be more precise, the meaning of this rule is: P_1 and P_2 are both assumed to have a common *center* pixel; P_1 occurs at pixel (n, m) of an image A if the shift of P_1 that moves its center to pixel (n, m) is contained in A . Thus, recognition of all occurrences of P_1 in A means identifying all pixels (n, m) where P_1 occurs in A ; all other pixels are removed from A . Subsequently, the substitution means composing a new image by taking copies of P_2 whose centers are placed at all pixels (n, m) found at the previous stage, and by superimposing these copies.

Here is an example of a rule of SS:

(here the center of the left pattern is its middle pixel, and the center of the right pattern is its singleton pixel).

Obviously, applying this rule to an image yields its interior (see Fig. 6.1 (a) and (b)) respectively).

Figure 6.1: An image, its interior and its boundary, respectively.

The operations which make symbolic substitution feasible, are correlation and convolution. To recognize any pattern p in an input image A one should correlate p and A . Suppose that p contains L pixels, and is given so that its center is at the origin. Then, obviously,

$$(A \odot p)_{nm} = \begin{cases} L, & \text{if } p_{nm} \subseteq A \\ < L, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where p_{nm} denotes the shift of pattern p with its center placed at pixel (n, m) .

Thus, the correlation has peaks of intensity at those pixels which correspond to occurrences of the center of P in A . Thus we need to threshold these peaks (provided we know the level of thresholding L , i.e. the size of the pattern p), thereby determining the locations of all these occurrences.

The next step is substitution of the found occurrences by another pattern P . To perform it, we simply convolve P with the δ -functions located at the peaks that we have thresholded.

The technique of simultaneous recognition of all occurrences of any pattern in a given image is the cornerstone of the algorithm described below.

6.2 The Idea Behind the Algorithm

To illustrate the idea of the algorithm, consider the continuous plane consisting of points rather than the discrete plane consisting of pixels. Let a figure A and a horizontal line $y = a$ intersecting A be given (see Fig. 6.2).

Figure 6.2: A figure intersected by a horizontal line.

What portions of this line lie in A ? To answer this question we assign a weight to each intersection point $(x_i(a), a)$ (where these points are assumed to be ordered from left to right) by the following recurrent formula:

$$weight(x_i(a), a) = \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} weight(x_k(a), a) + \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if the } i^{th} \text{ intersection is of} \\ & \text{the first type (as defined in Fig. 6.3);} \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if the } i^{th} \text{ intersection is of} \\ & \text{the second type (as defined in Fig. 6.4);} \\ -\frac{1}{2}, & \text{if the } i^{th} \text{ intersection is of} \\ & \text{the third type (as defined in Fig. 6.5);} \\ 0, & \text{if the } i^{th} \text{ intersection is of} \\ & \text{the fourth type (as defined in Fig. 6.6).} \end{cases}$$

The weight of a point, roughly speaking, is the number of intersections to its left where only intersections of the first type have weight 1, and the others have weight less than 1. If, for example, two intersections of the second type follow in succession they yield a real intersection. But if an intersection of the third type follows an intersection of the second type they cancel each other out.

Figure 6.3: Intersections of the first type; boundary segments are depicted as arrows in clockwise direction

Figure 6.4: Intersections of the second type; points of intersection are indicated as small circles.

Figure 6.5: Intersections of the third type.

Figure 6.6: Intersections of the fourth type.

It is easy to see that those segments of the line connecting pairs of consecutive intersection points, whose left endpoints have an odd (integral) weight, lie in (the interior of) A .

Now assign a type to each point p of ∂A to be the type of the intersection at p between ∂A and the horizontal line passing through p . Since interior points of horizontal boundary segments are not intersection points in the above sense, we assign to them the fourth type.

Thus, we have:

$$\partial A = \bigcup_{i=1}^4 S_i,$$

where S_i is the set of boundary points of the i^{th} type.

We can also assign a weight to other points (x, y) of the plane by the following formula:

$$weight(x, y) = \sum_{x_i(y) < x} weight(x_i(y), y).$$

The following proposition is obvious:

Proposition 6.2.1 *The interior of A is equal to the set of points of $\mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \partial A$ which have an odd (integral) weight.*

The following lemma gives us the way to compute $weight(x, y)$ provided we know the decomposition of ∂A into components $\{S_i\}_{i=1}^4$.

Lemma 6.2.2

$$weight(x, y) = (S_1 * ray)(x, y) + (S_2 * \frac{1}{2} \cdot ray)(x, y) + (S_3 * -[\frac{1}{2} \cdot ray])(x, y),$$

where

$$ray = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \geq 0, y = 0; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and convolution between a set S and any function $f(x, y)$ is defined as follows:

$$(S * f)(x, y) = (1_S * f)(x, y) = \sum_{(p, q) \in S} f(x - p, y - q).$$

Proof: It is easy to see that

$$weight(x, y) = \sum_{x_i(y) < x} weight(x_i(y), y) = n_1 + \frac{1}{2}n_2 - \frac{1}{2}n_3,$$

where n_1, n_2, n_3 are the number of intersections on the left of the point (x, y) having weights $1, \frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}$, respectively.

Since

$$ray(x - p, y - q) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \geq p, y = q; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

it follows that $\sum_{(p, q) \in S_i} ray(x - p, y - q)$ is the number of points of S_i that lie to the left of (x, y) . Thus, $(S_i * ray)(x, y) = n_i$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, and this is easily seen to imply the lemma.

□

Let us now turn from the plane consisting of points to the plane consisting of pixels. The approach described can easily be generalized to this setup, provided the given image has no holes, each boundary pixel touches both an interior pixel and an exterior pixel, and each boundary pixel has two and only two adjacent boundary pixels.

The first requirement stems from the fact that a pixel image cannot be uniquely reconstructed from its boundary if it contains holes. (For example, the boundary depicted on Fig. 6.7 (a) can be the boundary of both the image without a hole depicted on Fig. 6.7 (b) and the image with the hole depicted on Fig. 6.7 (c)).

Figure 6.7: An image with a hole can have the same boundary as an image without a hole

The second requirement stems from the definition of the boundary as a set of pixels having contacts both with the interior and the exterior of an image.

The third requirement stems from the fact that if each boundary pixel has two and only two adjacent boundary pixels, then we can satisfactorily assign each boundary pixel a type 1 – 4, in a similar way to types of boundary points in the continuous model (see Fig. 6.8 – 6.11 for the assignment of these types).

Figure 6.8: Pixels marked as 1 are boundary pixels of the first type.

Figure 6.9: Pixels marked as 2 are boundary pixels of the second type.

The generalization of the function $weight(x, y)$ is a matrix $WEIGHT(n, m)$ given by the following relationship:

$$WEIGHT(n, m) = (S_1 * RAY)(n, m) + (S_2 * \frac{1}{2} \cdot RAY)(n, m) - (S_3 * \frac{1}{2} \cdot RAY)(n, m),$$

where

$$RAY(n, m) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = 1, n \geq 1; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and S_i is now the set of boundary pixels of the i^{th} type, for $i = 1, 2, 3$.

It is easy to see that the interior of A consists only of those pixels (n, m) whose $WEIGHT(n, m)$ is odd, in analogy with Proposition 6.2.1, and, conversely, pixels having odd integral WEIGHT belong either to the interior or to the boundary of the image.

Figure 6.10: Pixels marked as 3 are boundary pixels of the third type.

Figure 6.11: Pixels marked as 4 are boundary pixels of the fourth type.

Hence, we can propose the following filling algorithm.

Step 1. For each $i = 1, 2, 3$ identify the boundary pixels of the i^{th} type. To do this, correlate the boundary with masks depicted on Fig. 6.8 – Fig. 6.10, respectively, and filter the resulting images at level 3. As a result we obtain images S_1, S_2 and S_3 .

Step 2. Compute

$$WEIGHT(n, m) = (S_1 * RAY)(n, m) + (S_2 * \frac{1}{2} \cdot RAY)(n, m) - (S_3 * \frac{1}{2} \cdot RAY)(n, m).$$

If we assume that the unit intensity is $\frac{\pi}{2a}$, where a is the parameter of sine-transform (see 1.1.2), then we can filter out pixels having odd integral WEIGHT as follows:

Step 3. Compute

$$W(n, m) = \sin^2(a \cdot WEIGHT(n, m)) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } WEIGHT(n, m) \text{ is odd;} \\ < 1, & \text{otherwise .} \end{cases}$$

Step 4. Compute

$$FILL(n, m) = W(n, m) - W(n, m) \cdot BOUNDARY(n, m),$$

where $BOUNDARY(n, m)$ is equal to 1 or 0 depending on whether the pixel (n, m) belongs to the boundary or not.

Since each step of the algorithm can be performed optically in constant time, we obtain:

Lemma 6.2.3 *The interior of a plane image without holes can be filled optically in constant time provided each boundary pixel touches two and only two other boundary pixels.*

The last condition is usually not satisfied at every boundary pixel. Nevertheless, there is a way of removing redundant pixels from the boundary, forcing it to satisfy the condition. The way to perform this is described in the following section.

6.3 How to Remove Redundant Pixels from the Boundary.

Let us assume that the boundary of an image has no self-contacts, i.e. the following combinations of boundary, interior and exterior pixels are forbidden:

Figure 6.12: Forbidden combinations of interior (black), boundary (gray), and exterior (white) pixels.

Following a common terminology in computer graphics, we say that an image is *4-connected*, if each pair of pixels in the image can be joined by a sequence of pixels using only up, down, left, or right moves.

Lemma 6.3.1 *If the boundary of a connected image has no self-contacts, then the image is 4-connected.*

Proof. Suppose that the image is not 4-connected even though its boundary has no self-contacts. This means that the image contains two corner-adjacent pixels (see Fig. 6.13 (a)) and we cannot add pixel 1 or 2 (as marked in the figure) to them to satisfy the assertion of the lemma. Hence, both pixels 1 and 2 do not belong to the image. However, they also cannot lie in its exterior because exterior and interior pixels cannot be side-adjacent. Hence, they are boundary pixels, but this contradicts the assumption that the boundary has no self-contacts.

□

Figure 6.13: An example of two corner-adjacent (a) and two side-adjacent (b) pixels, respectively.

In what follows we call a 4-connecting path (a path with only left, right, up and down moves) a *chain*. We also call a boundary pixel which is side-adjacent with two corner-adjacent boundary pixels a *corner pixel*.

Now we are in a position to state the following main lemma of this section:

Lemma 6.3.2 *A pixel of the boundary of an image, which has no self-contacts, touches two and only two other boundary pixels, provided the image has no holes and all corner pixels of its boundary are removed and replaced by an interior or an exterior pixel, depending on whether the pixel removed is side-adjacent to an interior pixel or not.*

Proof. Suppose to the contrary that the boundary contains a pixel adjacent to three other boundary pixels (or, in other words, having degree 3). There is only a constant number of possible arrangements of these 4 pixels, and we consider here only one of them, depicted on Fig. 6.14. The proof for the other configurations is analogous.

Figure 6.14: An example of a boundary pixel of degree 3.

Since the boundary contains no corner pixels, there are only two possibilities: either the pixel between pixels 3 and 4 is an interior pixel or an exterior pixel (see Fig. 6.15).

Figure 6.15: Two possible extensions of the previous figure.

In the first (second) case there is a chain of interior (exterior) pixels connecting this pixel and some interior (exterior) pixel adjacent to pixel 1. Having added pixels 1 and 2 to the chain, we obtain a closed chain of non-exterior (non-interior) pixels which separates the plane into two regions, both of which contain an exterior (interior) pixel, which is impossible in an image without holes (see Fig. 6.16).

□

Figure 6.16: A chain of non-exterior pixels separating two exterior pixels.

It follows from the above lemma that if we remove all corner pixels from the boundary of an image without holes (and replace them by appropriate interior or exterior pixels), then each remaining boundary pixel will be adjacent to only two other boundary pixels.

The recognition of corner pixels can be performed by correlation of the boundary with each of the following masks:

After they are recognized, corner pixels can then be removed and replaced by interior or exterior pixels, as appropriate. The following lemma asserts that the removal of corner pixels from the boundary of an image without holes, which has no self-contacts, does not change the topology of the image.

Lemma 6.3.3 *Removal of corner pixels from the boundary of an image without holes, which has no self-contacts, yields the boundary of a new image having the same interior as the previous image.*

Proof. The lemma states that removal of corner pixels do not break the boundary of an image and do not lead to a situation where interior and exterior pixels become side-adjacent. We will prove this for the first rule only. The proof for other rules is analogous.

First, recall that the removal of a corner pixel from the boundary means that it is replaced by an interior or exterior pixel. Such a replacement can break the topology iff the pixel removed (labeled as pixel 2 in Fig. 6.17) is side-adjacent with both an interior and

exterior pixel. However, in this case pixel 4 cannot be either interior or exterior because otherwise there would be a pair of side-adjacent interior and exterior pixels. Thus, pixel 4 must be a boundary pixel. However, since pixel 1 belongs to the boundary it must border on an interior pixel which can be connected with the black pixel indicated on Fig. 6.17 by a chain consisting of interior pixels. Having added pixels 1 and 2 to this chain, we obtain a chain of non-exterior pixels completely enveloping either pixel 3 or pixel 4. Since the image cannot contain a hole, either pixel 3 or pixel 4 is interior. However, this contradicts the assumption that they are both boundary pixels. The contradiction proves the lemma.

□

Figure 6.17: Configurations of boundary, interior and exterior pixels where removal of corner boundary pixel breaks the topology of an image

Based on these lemmas and lemma 6.2.3, we obtain the following main result of the paper:

Theorem 6.3.4 *An image without holes whose boundary has no self-contacts can be filled optically in constant time.*

Chapter 7

Optical Sorting Algorithm

Although sorting is not a geometric problem per se, it is still an important part of many algorithms in standard computational geometry. Although so far we managed to develop optical algorithms in computational geometry without having to apply sorting, it is conceivable that sorting will be required in future optical computational geometry algorithms. For this reason we include in this work an optical sorting algorithm.

There already exist several optical sorting algorithms. They can be classified according to their specific hardware configuration, time-complexity, space-complexity and restrictions on elements which can be sorted. The algorithm proposed by C. Stirk and R. Athale performs sorting on a mesh of optical processor elements, each of which can only perform comparisons between two values and distribute them to other processor elements depending on the result of the comparison. The algorithm has $O(\ln^2 N)$ time complexity and $O(N \ln^2 N)$ space-complexity and can sort only distinct elements [SA].

Two algorithms by J. Reif and A. Tyagi also can sort only distinct elements. However, the first algorithm has already $O(1)$ time-complexity and $O(N^2)$ space-complexity. The second algorithm has $O(\ln \ln N)$ time-complexity but $O(N^{1+\epsilon})$ space-complexity [RT]. These algorithms also work on a mesh of optical processor elements, which are however more sophisticated than those used in the previous algorithm: they can perform a discrete Fourier transform and scalar operations such as \times , $+$ and comparison with two inputs.

The optical sorting algorithm by A. Schuster and Y. Ben-Asher can sort any elements in constant time but has $O(N^3)$ space-complexity [SB]. This algorithm works on a dynamically reconfigurable network of optical processor elements, capable of performing a few simple operations like addition and comparison of input signals, reading signals from a bus, writing signals to a bus, disconnecting a processor element from a bus, etc.

This chapter contains the description of an optical sorting algorithm which can sort N non-distinct elements in constant time and has $O(N^2)$ space-complexity. The gain in space-complexity is achieved by using a single optical processor instead of a mesh of processors and by the way in which the elements to be sorted are represented on an SLM. This representation requires the use of optical matrix operations as primitives in the design of the sorting algorithm.

It is worth mentioning that the previous optical sorting algorithms were intended for implementation as an optical sorting network, and not on an optical matrix processor, because devising sorting networks is a standard approach to constructing sorting algorithms in conventional computer science. However, with the availability of all the sophisticated and specialized machinery in optical computing, we believe that other, less conventional approaches should be tried, which will most likely lead to better solutions.

7.1 Sorting by Matrix Operations

We continue to use in this chapter the discrete model of optical computation (see section 1.1.3). Let the sequence of discrete values to be sorted be a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N , and suppose that it is represented as the discrete brightness distribution of pixels which constitute a row of pixels on an input SLM. Then, sorting can be achieved by the following algorithm, whose input is the vector $\|a_1 \ a_2 \ \dots \ a_N\|$ (represented in this form).

Step 1. Compute the matrix $\|a_{ij}\|$ by the formula:

$$\|a_{ij}\| = \begin{vmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{vmatrix} \times \|a_1 \ a_2 \ \dots \ a_N\| = \begin{vmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_N \\ a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_N \end{vmatrix}.$$

Step 2. Compute $\|b_{ij}\| = \|a_{ij}\|^t$ by reflecting an SLM containing the matrix with respect to its diagonal.

Step 3. Compute $\|c_{ij}\| = \|a_{ij}\| - \|b_{ij}\| = \|a_j - a_i\|$.

Step 4. Compute

$$\|d_{ij}\| = \text{Threshold}_0^1(\|c_{ij}\|),$$

i.e.

$$d_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a_i \leq a_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Since we assume that an SLM can only represent discrete and well distinguishable levels of brightness rather than real numbers, this operation is stable and cannot lead to ambiguities.

Step 5. Compute

$$\|e_i\| = \|d_{ij}\| \times \begin{vmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} \sum_{j=1}^N d_{1j} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{j=1}^N d_{Nj} \end{vmatrix},$$

so that e_i shows how many numbers in the sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N are not less than the number a_i .

Step 6. Compute

$$\|f_i\| = \begin{vmatrix} N+1 \\ \vdots \\ N+1 \end{vmatrix} - \|e_i\|.$$

Clearly, if all the a_i are different, then f_i would give the place of a_i in the sorted sequence. However, if $a_i = a_j$, then $f_i = f_j$. In this case the place of a value a_i in the sorted sequence is determined by the expression

$$\overline{f}_i = f_i + \#\{j|j < i \ \& \ f_j = f_i\},$$

where $\#S$ denotes the cardinality of the set S .

The further steps are needed for computing this vector $\|\overline{f}_i\|$.

Step 7. Compute

$$\|g_{ij}\| = \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ \vdots \\ f_N \end{Bmatrix} \times \begin{Bmatrix} 1 & \dots & 1 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 & f_1 & \dots & f_1 \\ f_2 & f_2 & \dots & f_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ f_N & f_N & \dots & f_N \end{Bmatrix}.$$

Step 8. Compute $\|h_{ij}\| = \|g_{ij}\|^t$.

Step 9. Compute $\|k_{ij}\| = \|g_{ij}\| - \|h_{ij}\| = \|f_i - f_j\|$.

Step 10. Compute $\|\overline{k}_{ij}\| = \|h_{ij}\| - \|g_{ij}\| = \|f_j - f_i\|$.

Step 11. Compute $\|l_{ij}\| = \text{Threshold}_0^1(\|k_{ij}\|)$, where

$$l_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f_i \geq f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 12. Compute $\|m_{ij}\| = \text{Threshold}_0^1(\|\overline{k}_{ij}\|)$, where

$$m_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f_i \leq f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 13. Compute $\|n_{ij}\| = \|l_{ij}\| \cdot \|m_{ij}\|$. Obviously,

$$n_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f_i = f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 14. Compute $\|\overline{g}_{ij}\| = \|g_{ij}\| \cdot \|n_{ij}\|$. It is clear that

$$\overline{g}_{ij} = \begin{cases} f_i, & \text{if } f_i = f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 15. Compute

$$\|\overline{n}_{ij}\| = \begin{Bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \times \|n_{ij}\|.$$

It is easy to see that $\overline{n}_{ij} = \#\{k|n_{kj} = 1; k \leq i\}$.

Step 16. Compute $\|p_{ij}\| = \|\overline{n_{ij}}\| \cdot \|n_{ij}\|$, so $p_{ij} = \#\{k|n_{kj} = 1; k \leq i; n_{ij} = 1\} = \#\{k|f_k = \overline{f_j}; f_i = f_j; k \leq i\}$.

Step 17. Compute $\|q_{ij}\| = \|\overline{g_{ij}}\| + \|p_{ij}\|$. It is easy to see that

$$q_{ij} = \begin{cases} f_i + \#\{k|f_k = f_j; f_i = f_j; k \leq i\}, & \text{if } f_i = f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

In other words,

$$q_{ij} = \begin{cases} f_i + \#\{k|f_k = f_i; k \leq i\}, & \text{if } f_i = f_j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 18. Compute

$$\|r_{ij}\| = \|q_{ij}\| \cdot \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{vmatrix},$$

i.e.

$$r_{ij} = \begin{cases} f_i + \#\{k|f_k = f_i; k \leq i\}, & \text{if } i = j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 19. Compute

$$\|s_i\| = \|r_{ij}\| \times \begin{vmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{vmatrix},$$

i.e. $s_i = f_i + \#\{k|f_k = f_i; k \leq i\}$.

Step 20. Compute

$$\|\overline{f_i}\| = \|s_i\| - \begin{vmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{vmatrix},$$

i.e. $\overline{f_i} = f_i + \#\{k|f_k = f_i; k < i\}$.

Thus, we have computed the vector $\|\overline{f_i}\|$, every element of which indicates the place of the corresponding value a_i in the sorted sequence. The next part of our algorithm is intended for transforming this vector into the matrix $\|x_{ij}\|$, which satisfies the condition:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a_i \text{ stands at place } j \text{ in the sorted sequence (i.e. } \overline{f_i} = j); \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 21. Compute

$$\|t_{ij}\| = \|\overline{f_i}\| \times \|1 \dots 1\|.$$

Step 22. Compute

$$\|u_{ij}\| = \|t_{ij}\| - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 & \dots & N \\ 1 & 2 & \dots & N \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 2 & \dots & N \end{vmatrix},$$

i.e. $u_{ij} = \bar{f}_i - j$.

Step 23. Compute $\|v_{ij}\| = -\|u_{ij}\|$.

Step 24. Compute $\|y_{ij}\| = \text{Threshold}_0^1(\|u_{ij}\|)$, i. e.

$$y_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \bar{f}_i \geq j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 25. Compute $\|z_{ij}\| = \text{Threshold}_0^1(\|v_{ij}\|)$, i. e.

$$z_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \bar{f}_i \leq j; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Step 26. Compute $\|x_{ij}\| = \|y_{ij}\| \cdot \|z_{ij}\|$,

Thus, we have computed the required matrix $\|x_{ij}\|$. It is obvious that the multiplication $\|a_j\| \times \|x_{ij}\|$ yields the sorted sequence. Therefore, the next step completes the sorting.

Step 27. Compute $\|\bar{a}_i\| = \|a_j\| \times \|x_{ij}\|$.

It is easy to see that, since every step of this algorithm can be performed by an optical computer, simultaneously for all i, j , in constant time (in the discrete model of computation), the time complexity of the algorithm is $O(1)$. Thus:

Theorem 7.1.1 *One can sort a sequence of N real numbers in a constant number of optical operation in the discrete model, using an optical matrix processor.*

Chapter 8

Conclusion

In the conclusion of this thesis we would like to summarize the work done and outline the problems that still remain unsolved.

First, we have enumerated an exhaustive list of the main mathematical operations for which it was already demonstrated in practice that they can be performed optically in constant time, and combined them into two basic optical models of computations, the continuous and the discrete models. Furthermore, we have initiated the design and analysis of algorithms based on these operations as new primitives, and called them optical algorithms. In fact, we have laid the foundation of the theory of optical algorithms, in this setting, and, in particular, devised many computational tricks for constructing efficient algorithms of this kind, and applied them to solving optically and efficiently most of the basic problems of planar computational geometry. We have found that practically all of these problems, with the exception of Voronoi diagrams, triangulations, and reconstructing the boundary of a polygon from its vertices, can be solved optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the monochromatic mode. The latter three problems can also be solved optically in constant time using a single optical processor which works in the polychromatic mode. However, the possibility of solving them in constant time using the monochromatic mode of optical computations remains an important open problem.

We would like to conclude this thesis with a list of unsolved problems, and would like to elaborate on possible further development of optical computational geometry and of computer graphics.

The following problems seem to be most appropriate for the subsequent research:

- Design of efficient and parallel techniques for transferring data between electronic and optical computers;
- Constructing a spanning tree and a minimum spanning tree of a point set in the plane;
- Finding the shortest path between vertices in a planar graph;
- Constructing the shortest path among obstacles in the plane;
- Constructing the relative convex hull of a given point set inside a polygonal region [T];
- Constructing the smallest circle containing a given point set;
- Placing a maximum homothetic copy of a figure inside another figure;

- Constructing the maximum empty circle touching at least three points of a given point set in the plane;
- Planar graph drawing;

Another direction for further research concerns *robustness* of optical algorithms. In our models of optical computation we have made several ideal assumptions, whose practical implementation may be more problematic. For example, in certain algorithms we made use of filters capable of distinguishing between many levels of brightness. Also, practical handling of the δ -function requires a certain amount of approximation. There are other optical operations, e.g. differentiation used in edge detection, that are likely to be more sensitive to even slightly noisy data. All these issues call for further study of techniques of making optical algorithms more robust, similar to current studies in standard computational geometry (see e.g. [Fo]).

Another possible direction of subsequent development of optical computational geometry is its generalization to three-dimensional and high-dimensional cases. Optics definitely has means for representation of multi-dimensional images using frequency, polarization, and other parameters of light waves, as supplementary coordinates of an image, in addition to the standard X, Y -coordinates. Optics also has means to manipulate these parameters, such as adding frequencies of two light waves, etc. Undoubtedly, using these generalized coordinates will require revising our optical models of computation. However, here it is probably the case that not all components of this new model already exist in the physical and optical engineering literature, as was the case for the two-dimensional optical computational model. More likely, substantiating such a new model of optical computing will require cooperation between optical computational geometers and optical scientists (both engineers and physicists), in devising new operations on high-dimensional images and their optical realization.

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